

Evaluation of the Archivematica Ingest Functionality
Metadata and Rights Management for Digital Data Objects of Local Authorities

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Abstract

Archivematica is an open-source and non-commercial digital preservation system, that was chosen and installed by the National Library of Wales to explore the ingest and preservation of digital data-objects, as part of the digital preservation ambitions of the Archives and Records Council Wales. The aim of the dissertation is to comprehend the operating principles of Archivematica 1.5 and evaluate the transfer and ingest functionality for digital data-objects of Local Authorities. This dissertation applies multiple research methods to cross-validate the findings on the Archivematica ingest functionality and the according metadata and rights management. In addition to a comprehensive literature review, and the technical analysis of the Archivematica ingest, a mostly qualitative data collection captures the current situation in Welsh digital preservation institutions regarding metadata and rights management. The final research method targets the criteria-based evaluation of the Archivematica ingest according to the recommendations of the Producer-Archive Interface Methodology Standard. The results show, that Archivematica provides interfaces to enter descriptive metadata compliant to Dublin Core, and administrative metadata compliant to PREMIS. To create a submission ready data-set, the data-objects benefit from descriptive metadata input with the aid of a CSV-file. The automatic extraction and processing of descriptive metadata from a CSV-file is enabled by Archivematica 1.5, however administrative metadata cannot be handled in that manner yet. The small-scale purposive data collection through executing a mostly open-ended questionnaire revealed that copyright and license regulation are predominant. The need for a digital preservation system and capturing metadata is bridged by applying cataloguing software. The criteria based evaluation of the ingest functionality of Archivematica confirmed the good quality of the technical architecture of this digital preservation system. Archivematica's ability to be adjusted and extended by other software for transfer and pre-ingest storage, and access is beneficial for the adaption to current needs and circumstances of the archive.

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Abbreviations

ARCW	:	Archives and Records Council Wales
AtOM	:	Access to Memory
CMS	:	Content Management System
CSV	:	Comma Separated Value
DP	:	Digital Preservation
DPA	:	Data Protection Act
DPS	:	Digital Preservation System
Fedora	:	Flexible Extensible Digital Object Repository Architecture
FOI	:	Freedom of Information
EDRMS	:	Electronic Document and Records Management System
HTML	:	Hyper Text Mark-up Language
IP	:	Intellectual Property
IPR	:	Intellectual Property Rights
JPEG2000	:	Joint Photographic Experts Group 2000
LIFS	:	Linked File System
METS	:	Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard
MD	:	Metadata
OAIS	:	Open Archival Information System
PDF	:	Portable Document Format
RM	:	Records Management
RMS	:	Records Management System
SGML	:	Standard Generalized Mark-up Language

TIFF : Tagged Image File Formats
UI : User Interface
XML : Extensible Mark-up Language
XMP : Extensible Metadata Platform

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I Introduction

1.1 Background

The Open Archival Information System (OAIS) is an internationally recognized and established reference model, which includes a framework for long term preservation and access of digital objects, and an information model defining the administrated and operated information entities. It was introduced in 2003 and revised in 2012 and builds the basis for current ambitions in standardizing digital preservation and implementing adequate information systems. Following the separation of information packages as submission (SIP), archival (AIP), or dissemination information packages (DIP), the OAIS environment features three main stages: ingest, preservation and access. While digital preservation mainly takes place within the technical OAIS conformant system and therefore focusses on the archival information package, the ingest- and pre-ingest phases are a crucial predecessor for the success and longevity of the preservation workflow (Kärberg, 2013, p.85). With information systems like Archivematica and Preservica, two acknowledged tools have been created, tested and made available for OAIS application. The Archives and Records Council Wales (ARCW) Digital Preservation Consortium is aiming to provide a software solution for all Archives in Wales to handle digital preservation on their own and cooperate with the superordinate institutions. Therefore, the consortium decided to rely on freely available open-source software with no licensing fees and restrictions and picked Archivematica as the digital preservation system of choice. The OAIS environment is established and tested for ingesting and converting information packages.

ARCW wants to provide a reasonable and working software setting for all archives in Wales, accompanied by guidance for practical approaches “where people could start to actually handle digital objects and learn by doing” (ARCW, 2015). Part of the current approaches of the consortium is to create pre-ingest documentation, including hardware recommendations, ICT business cases, deposit templates and guidance sheets for depositors (National Archives, 2014). Taking the Conwy Archives Collection Management Policy as an example of good policy creation and collection management, it also displays the variety of sources for the records and document acquisition archival repositories deal with: official council records, governmental protocols, public records, ecclesiastical records, official publications of societies, organizations etc. These files get published in EDRMS, online on municipal websites and locally on

storage media of the creator. Collecting the final data, adding the appropriate context information and transferring it to the preservation system are obstacles these institutions face on an infrastructural and cognitive level.

1.2 Purpose

Since the technical infrastructure is in place, the focus shifts to understanding how the digital preservation system works and how to handle file conversion, metadata enhancement and rights management. Archivemata was created to support the ingest and submission of digital objects. The main issues of dealing with information objects in the Pre-Ingest and Ingest Phase include:

- Digitally born material of all kind, hybrid collections of partially analogue and digital files/ records and collections of digital files with various file formats, partially outdated, partially proprietary.
- Gathering and linking correct and complete metadata to each and every file, while integrating the data sets into the collection and subsequently into the superior fonds.
- Allocating and manage licenses, agreements and rights concerning copyright, intended use, editing allowance of metadata and preservation allowance.
- Clearly distinguishing the tasks and responsibilities for SIP creators in terms of metadata requirements, file formats, normalization and general description.
- Establishing at what point the archives takes over responsibility for the SIP.

1.3 Aims and Objectives

Archivemata provides a transfer and an ingest area, including metadata editing and rights management in the user interface. The aim of the dissertation is to comprehend the operating principles of the digital preservation system Archivemata and evaluate the transfer and ingest functionality for digital data objects.

The research objectives include the following:

1. Identify given metadata information in the existing files and identify minimum metadata requirements.
2. Assess necessary file migration, meta-data enrichment and additional context information. What needs to be provided by the submitter and what needs to be added by the archive?
3. Determine how a *good* SIP is constructed: what the necessary components are and best practices on how to create solid information packages ready for submission into Archivematica.
4. Evaluate the usability of the Archivematica ingest function to manage metadata and intellectual property rights.

1.4 Scope

The provided Archivematica installation at the National Library of Wales (NLW) is currently in testing with several people working on different issues in the technical, use and adapting areas. To provide a first approach on how to use Archivematica for local authority data object, this dissertation limits the file variety to the most popular ones in Welsh administrative bodies and archives: text, spreadsheets, and PDF (Henry, 2016). Due to the early stages of the implementation and testing of Archivematica in Wales, this investigation uses small scale data sets and object registries. The transfer and ingest of large scale collections and object registries will not be explored. Subsequently the data sets contain closed single data objects; tests with multi-file objects (e.g. documents linking other media elements or other documents) are not conducted.

The primary data collection instrument, applying a self-administrated questionnaire, targets a group of the Welsh digital preservation community, since the Archivematica installation is supposed to be a solution for the Welsh archives community. The purpose of the questionnaire is to capture the current situation concerning metadata management, rights management and negotiations between data producer and archives.

1.5 Structure

This dissertation applies four research actions to answer the abovementioned research objectives: a literature review, a technical analysis of the Archivemática transfer and ingest functionalities; a purposive small-sample data collection; and finally a criteria-based evaluation of the usability of the ingest functionality of Archivemática. Due to this methodological triangulation, each research action is explored in a chapter in this dissertation. The chapter structure includes an introduction, a methodological discourse, the results and conclusion. To provide the overall research approach and to introduce digital preservation *Chapters 2 and 3* precede the literature review. The appendices include supplementary graphs, tables and figures for each chapter. Synthesizing the insights and findings are in *Chapters 5 to 7*, the discussion chapter (*Chapter 8*) provides the bigger picture. Finally, the conclusion (*Chapter 9*) summarizes the dissertation and critically investigates the research methods and results before providing recommendations.

II Introduction to Digital Preservation and OAIS / PAIMAS

This chapter intends to give a brief introduction to digital preservation, the examined digital preservation system Archivematica, and the applied Producer-Archive Interface Methodology Abstract Standard (PAIMAS). Digital preservation inherits a set of terms and definition that are important to be aware of to understand concepts and connections. The following digest provides an overview of concepts to acknowledge based on OAIS terminology:

“Authenticity: The degree to which a person (or system) regards an object as what it is purported to be. Authenticity is judged on the basis of evidence.” (CSSDS, 2012, p. 19)

“Information Package: A logical container composed of optional Content Information and optional associated Preservation Description Information. Associated with this Information Package is Packaging Information used to delimit and identify the Content Information and Package Description Information used to facilitate searches for the Content Information.” (CSSDS, 2012, p.22)

“Designated Community: An identified group of potential Consumers who should be able to understand a particular set of information. The Designated Community may be composed of multiple user communities. A Designated Community is defined by the Archive and this definition may change over time.” (CSSDS, 2012, p.21)

For further information, please see PAIMAS (CSSDS, 2004) and OAIS (CSSDS, 2012) terminology overviews to see full set of definitions and terms.

“Digital documents last forever – or five years, whichever comes first.” (Rothenberg, 1999) is a popular quote that captures one of the main drivers for digital preservation. Format obsolescence, readability, and cost-intensive preservation methods such as format migration or emulation are coherent to the technical innovation and progression of digital things. Just like preservation for analogue material, digital preservation follows processes and activities to secure permanent and loss-free storage of the digital information. In order to maintain the correct file format and representation, as well as access and readability several preservation strategies developed over time. With transforming the format as the technology changes, migration is one popular choice. In contrast to upgrading and altering the digital data objects, emulation retains the original state of the digital object and creates the application software

and program environments in contemporary technologies to emulate the original behaviour and representation. Regardless of the selected method there are specific actions that are necessary to follow through to safeguard the digital objects for long term storage and future access. Ideally the original data bit stream and a corresponding preservation version of the original data object is retained, which are both securely stored. Additionally, data is cleaned, validated and provided with an acceptable data structure to increase future retrieval and re-use. To improve the preservation, discovery and potential use preservation metadata and information is added (Paradigm, 2008).

To safeguard the future user's ability to comprehend the content and context of the information stored in the digital object, and to preserve a consistent digital collection, metadata occupy an important role in the digital preservation elements. With the embedded information, access, understanding and authenticity of the corresponding digital object can be documented and managed (SAA, 2002). In order to provide a complete set of information about the digital object, metadata functions include descriptive, technical, administrative, use, and preservation information (Higgins, 2007). Further information about the different types of metadata and several standards such as PREMIS, Dublin Core and METS are discussed in *Chapter 4*.

Originally set out to provide a structured digital preservation and long term archiving approach for research data, the Open Archival Information System (OAIS) is one of the established frameworks to handle digital data. Software solutions based on the OAIS built an information architecture that tackles the risks to digital data.

Figure 1: OAIS model with entities.

The OAIS environment consist of three entities that stand in relation to the archive/repository (Paradigm, 2008) (Figure 1):

- Producer (provides and delivers digital material such as data objects and context information)
- Management (manages and preserves submitted material)
- Consumer (requests and obtains digital material)

Figure 2: OAIS functional model with repository activities.

As depicted in Figure 2, the functional model contains the preservation specific activities that are executed in the OAIS archive. The names of the functionalities are: ingest; archival storage; administration; data management; preservation planning; and access (Paradigm, 2008).

Figure 3: OAIS information model with information packages.

Figure 3 shows that the next layer in this reference model is the information model, which focusses on the significant components of created information packages in each phase of the functional model. The digital objects to be preserved, appropriate metadata, and packaging information are the main elements of each Information Package (IP). The OAIS contains one Information Package for each stage: submission, archive and, dissemination. The submission information package (SIP) is provided by the producer and includes the original data objects and metadata that forms a data-set ready for ingest. After the submission of the data-set, the information package is transformed to an archival information package (AIP). The original data object is supplemented by a preservation version of that file, the provided metadata might lack structure and preservation relevant information and is enhanced to meet a preservation metadata standard. The data-set provided for the consumer's request is called the dissemination information package (DIP) and contains the data-object and relevant metadata (Paradigm, 2008).

Figure 4: Information Object consists of the Data Object and its Representation Information.

The information object combines the data object with the associated representation information (CCSDS, 2012, p.64-73) (Figure 4). The structural or semantic representation information are used to interpret the data object, which can originate from a physical or digital object. For example, the data object is a text file created with Microsoft Word 2003 and uses the .doc format extension, that implies that software is needed that is able to render this specific Microsoft Word Standard to depict the information object authentic and integral. Combining the data object with its representation information results in content information and is the main target for digital preservation. Context information is necessary to display the meaning of the information object in the collection or relationships to other information objects. Specific information about content, preservation description, packaging, and general descriptions are some of the possible supplementary information that can be added to enrich the preservation of an information object.

Figure 5: Preservation Description Information contains 5 information categories.

OAIS uses the term Preservation Description Information (PDI) for vital information to safeguard the digital object properly. PDI include reference information (persistent identifier), provenance information (object history), context information (structure of collection or archive), fixity information (checksum to validate correct transfer) (CCSDS, 2012, p.72-73) (Figure 5).

Archivemata is based on OAIS and provides a web-interface in addition to the freely available open-source digital preservation system (Artefactual Inc., 2015). The Linux built repository is the core element of Archivemata and is supplemented by transfer, and access environments. Access to Memory (AtoM) is a compatible discovery and access architecture for Archivemata. Archivemata uses the information and functional model of OAIS: the provided areas in the web-interface include transfer, ingest, preservation planning, and access. Each area is features with a set of micro-services to apply and process the preservation activities, and subsequently follow through the transformation from SIP, to AIP to DIP. A detailed explanation of the transfer and ingest functionality of Archivemata is provided in *Chapter 5*.

The Producer-Archive Interface Method Abstract Standard was developed to support and guide the interaction between data producer and archive in the OAIS environment. It's focus is on the pre-ingest and ingest phase of OAIS with the intention to identify and define submission details and create a submission agreement. Guiding through the preliminary, formal definition, transfer, and validation phase, the recommendations feature actions and settlements, and establish initially preliminary agreement, followed by a submission agreement, and finally the validation agreement at the end of each phase (CCSDS, 2004, p.10-11). Further information about PAIMAS and the relation to Archivemata as OAIS environment is depict in *Chapter 7*.

III Overview Methodology

This chapter intends to provide a methodological digest of this dissertation. As the table of contents show the dissertation is split according to the research actions taken, featured with detailed methodology explanation and justification. The aim of the dissertation is to comprehend the operating principles of the digital preservation system Archivemata and evaluate the transfer and ingest functionality for digital data objects. Subsequently the desired outcome of the system evaluation is the determination of an example submission information package (SIP) for digital objects originating in local authorities. To provide a valid and qualitative investigation this dissertation applies mixed methods to corroborate its findings. The methodological triangulation consists of a small-scale purposive questionnaire to capture qualitative data, and a criteria-based evaluation of the information system. Additionally, the insights from the literature review, results from a recent digital preservation survey (Henry, 2016), and information from the Archivemata documentation (Artefactual Inc., 2015) provide further dimensions. This source triangulation intends to amplify the consistency of the data sources and subsequently validate the research outcomes.

The literature review intends to give a digest of digital preservation and metadata management, and experiences with pre-ingest and ingest of digital data objects to capture the latest development and insights from the community. Primary and secondary sources are used while commercial solutions and data from the health sector are avoided to keep the focus on public archives. The next step is to analyse and understand the transfer and ingest functionalities of Archivemata.

This first system evaluation intends to determine the most effective and efficient way to create a complete and consistent submission information package (SIP), containing digital data objects, metadata information and rights information. In order to accomplish that a series of tests were executed with the differently created SIPs. The evaluation measure in this case is the METS XML file that is generated by Archivemata for each SIP. Focussing on the METS sections, the quality of descriptive and administrative metadata, which play a crucial part for the preservation objectives of a digital preservation system, is the vital benchmark for the evaluation of the ingest functionality of Archivemata.

The following step is to gather insights on current practices and circumstances for metadata and intellectual rights management, and access management in Welsh digital preservation institutions. A group of people with digital preservation background and experience with depositor negotiations form the purposive non-probability sample. This research approach intends to capture highly subjective answers from a homogenous and limited population to validate the insights from the literature review and the Archivemata ingest functionality testing. Mixed methods of mostly qualitative open-ended questions, and a number of quantitative multiple-choice questions was chosen for data collection.

The final step is to evaluate the pre-ingest activities of Archivemata based on a criteria catalogue provided by the Producer-Archive Interface Mythology Abstract (PAIMAS). That standard is set out to provide guidance and recommendations to negotiate submission circumstances and the SIP quality between the data depositor (also known as data producer) and the archive (in this case an institution with Archivemata). The Archivemata installation used in this dissertation research is in testing mode and not officially available yet, the access system AtoM was not available during this research. Due to the limited resources of this dissertation the author decided to only focus on the preliminary phase of PAIMAS and not follow through the formal definition phase, transfer phase, and validation phase.

The first three research objectives stated in 1.3 will be covered in the literature review (*Chapter 4*) and added to insights from the Archivemata tests (*Chapter 5*) and questionnaire answers (*Chapter 6*). Objective 4 relies predominantly on the criteria based evaluation with PAIMAS (*Chapter 7*) and the answers from the participants to PAIMAS related questions (*Chapter 6*).

IV Literature Review

4.1 Introduction

Before testing Archivematica and exploring the current situation regarding SIP creation in Welsh archives a comprehensive literature review is necessary to provide insights on digital preservation, metadata management and experiences with setting up information systems to support data submission. This chapter is divided into four parts covering records management and digital preservation, insights and experiences from other projects and approaches, how metadata management was executed, and the latest insights on pre-ingest and ingest procedures. Finally, the conclusion provides the base for the subsequent discussion in *Chapter 5* of this dissertation. The intention is to provide information from the literature for all four Research Objectives.

4.2 Methodology

Both primary and secondary data collection was applied in this research. The literature review intends to give an overview of the link between records management and digital preservation:

- Lessons learned about ingest and metadata management in other projects;
- Approaches on managing metadata; and
- Recognising of the pre-ingest and ingest phases in the digital preservation community.

The search strategy for information and references included:

- Reflecting on the previous master's dissertation about risk management in records management; information governance in local authorities; records management in repositories with cloud computing; file format migration and refreshment in public archival repositories; and digital repositories in local authority archives services.
- Referencing printed books about metadata management; digital curation; digital collection management; institutional repositories; information organization and retrieval from the university library collections.

- Electronic articles and materials were filtered to focus on experiences with OAIS; digital preservation; ingest and pre-ingest functions in digital archives; file formats and metadata harvesting; the Archive Ingest and Handling Test; submission information package containers; and linking and representing data and metadata.
- Consulting existing frameworks such as the OAIS Reference Model and PAIMAS.

Using the online library catalogues and databases provided by the library and information services of Aberystwyth University, the information retrieval with Boolean operators and truncation, aimed to focus on literature about digital archives and public repositories, preferably with local authority context. The literature review covers insights and implementation in the research community as well, avoiding the health sector and commercial solutions. The main focus lay on metadata management, licensing and alteration rights, and file format alteration (refreshing, migrating, and normalizing).

4.3 Records Management and Digital Preservation Intertwined

Reviewing how and why historical traditions and cultural memories are recovered and discovered reveals that paper based records often survived by mistake and thanks to the longevity of the storage media and the readability without necessary viewers or devices (Oliver and Harvey, 2016, p.159). Evaluating the present situation and emergent themes, the majority of content is created digitally and needs electronic devices as well as software for rendering and readability. Today, fragmented records with partially printed paper manifestations and partially digital manifestations are quite common (Duranti, 2010). To distinguish the terms *document* and *record* in records management (RM) terms leads to the perspective that documents can be edited continuously and records are final and fixed versions of documents. With added links between content, record structures and context the document grows in the course of several working versions to record status (Smallwood, 2013, p.274). Digital objects highly likely do not survive by mistake, certainly not in a trustworthy and readable manifestation (Ames et al., 2005, p.10). Therefore, the active preservation of digital objects needs to take constant actions to assure that digital objects outlast time in a readable, authentic and integral manner.

Records management systems (RMS) help local authorities and governmental administration to manage, retain and dispose of documents and records created in every day work, as well as vital records for the institutional compliance to legislative and regulatory requirements such as the Freedom of Information Act, 2000 (FOI) and the Data Protection Act, 1998 (DPA). In order to guarantee a properly running RMS a uniform understanding among all participating content creators has to be in place, including people being aware of personal responsibility while creating and sharing documents and subsequently creating records. Referring to Parker (1989) the issues with document filing and retrieval continue to impact electronic records in the same manner; multiple-copy files in several places, and being able just to retrieve a fraction of filed documents (Johnstone, 2012, p.82, 83). Based on legislative and regulatory demands to conform to information governance in Local Authorities, RM has also to deal with digital preservation (DP) and long-term archiving of their documents. In order to deal with DP demands, RM has to evolve to an achievable and sustainable workflow that creates trustworthy records, which are not restricted by intellectual or technological risks (Kaye, 2011, p.37, 38). While RM covers regular information and documents, which come in all sizes and shapes with fully/ semi/ no structure, DP focusses also on vital records which have business importance. Therefore, a separation between every day records and unique information is necessary; institutions of civil services in England and Wales have to comply with the Disclosure of Electronic Documents Directive and can be fined for unstructured or insufficient data and inadequate metadata (Ministry of Justice, 2013).

The use of embedded metadata supports automated RM processes and thereby enabling information retrieval based on information characteristics. In order to achieve trustworthy and reliable documents with included metadata, the object and description has to remain inextricably linked (Kaye, 2011, p.62, 66, 68). Effective Content Management System (CMS) core functions must provide: versioning of documents for simultaneous editing and file history monitoring; quality control of content including assessment and quality assurance; and document type integration to store and deliver content appropriate to the demand. These characteristics provide provenance of files facilitating traceability and therefore comply with authenticity and controlling demands (Haynes, 2004, p.107, 127). In combination with RM policies an Electronic Document and Record Management System (EDRMS) aspires to store all documents and records in one place and linked to each other. Latest developments show a)

the development to multi-file documents and records, and b) aggregation within systems that unite all the information. The terms *document* for working files and compilations, and *record* for finalised creations will remain, however the variety of document types will increase and evolve. Subsequently EDRMS and digital preservation systems (DPS) have to evolve with their content and language. Alongside information governance (IG) policies, new classification schemes with identifiers for local authority content and taxonomies for evolving document types are needed (Kaye, 2011, p.71-74, 77-78).

The revolutionary improvements of letterpress, bounded papers and standard paper formats by Johannes Gutenberg have influenced a century of administrative processes. Today's 21st century digital society inexorably impacts upon a set of standardisation and pushes the boundaries of document shapes towards open ended, linked and modular forms. File systems in digital devices mirrored the long-term method of shelving of files and records in real life, hierarchical storing approaches being the appropriate way to deposit and store electronic files. With cloud storage and non-hierarchical file structures, technology and service providers aspire to new ways (Cockram, 2011, p.5-6). The demands on a DPS in terms of core requirements include: lossless and authentic data maintenance; discovery and retrieval of data by users; interpreting and understanding of data by users; and that all these requirements can be achieved at any time in the future (Jones et al., 2006, p.77). Chowdhury and Chowdhury (2007, p.188-189) summarized the main drivers for information architecture as the following: the need for proper access to and sharing of information; the increasing volume of digital information; uncoordinated and unplanned creation and management of information; heterogeneous information resources; fast growing information; difficulties related to query formulation; and different, and often non-standard, use of vocabulary. Within this, five risk factors of data exist: technological obsolescence; technological fragility; lack of understanding about what constitutes good practice; inadequate resources; and finally the uncertainties about the best organizational infrastructures to achieve effective digital curation (Oliver and Harvey, 2016, p.4).

4.4 Lessons Learned

Latest developments towards storing and sharing data using cloud computing technology lead to new challenges for RM and IG in terms of ownership, legal admissibility and data protection, which initiated the point of view that “technological elegance must be secondary to strategic records management” and networked approaches to share tools and services (Kaye, 2011, p. 60, 74-76). Alongside ownership questions, retaining rights are another difficulty originating from authors not retaining their rights on submitted material (Jones et al., 2006, p.154). During the decades a number of projects developed different ways of applying file format migration in the data lifecycle, for example on command entry level, at access points or avoiding migration by only accepting data in long-term storage compliant file formats (Sheldon, 2010, p.15). Citing Weibel, Iannella and Cathro (1997), metadata-standard schools can be divided between the minimalists and the structuralists. As the names imply the minimalist prefer simple metadata sets, the structuralists aim for formal metadata standards (Chowdhury and Chowdhury, 2007, p.144). According to Oliver and Harvey (2016) the most common metadata standards focus on preservation metadata by providing implementation strategies, encoding and transmission standards, and description schemas, based on extensible mark-up language (XML) to enable standardized of metadata expressions (Oliver and Harvey, 2016, p.73). Using XML as a base the Xena software provides electronic normalizing for archives, detecting proprietary and not proprietary file formats and converting them to open formats. The InSpect Project categorized significant properties of digital objects and databases as content, context, appearance, behaviour, and structure (Oliver and Harvey, 2016, p.118).

Waugh (2007) suggests to separate the normalisation of metadata from the pre-ingest process, hence the multiple systems producing digital objects, using different metadata schemes and data formats. Depending on the agency creating the data object and metadata sets, the types of source systems and technical resources differ from the resources and systems the archive has to open, check and edit the submitted data. Therefore, the content and metadata normalisation made by the original creator with their original software environment is beneficial in terms of resources and organisational knowledge.

The digital archive of the Public Record Office Victoria in Australia designed the ingest function with following features:

- early validation of digital objects;
- handling bulk ingest of digital objects;
- enabling grouping, isolating and reporting error-prone digital objects;
- enabling even minor correction in flawed digital objects; and
- only accepting the responsibility for digital objects after they have been stored in the digital repository.

In addition, a set of minimum requirements was established: a set contains all manifested objects; the SIP is encapsulated correctly; mandatory metadata is complete and present; file formats for the content objects are in long-term preservation conformant formats; and virus checks for all objects. Reflecting on the set-up and implementation of the ingest process Waugh points towards more parameters while the set is created; automated transfer from inbox to quarantine after validation; automatic creation of reports; and reviewing rights and tools for archivists at any process stage. Most importantly a new stage where archivists decide and approve whether they accept the set and the responsibility for it. In conclusion the evaluation of the design and implementation of an ingest function to the digital archive of the public record office in Victoria suggests separation of the normalization process from the ingest process by isolating, externally correct and resubmitting the new set, rather than to correct the flawed set in the ingest area (Waugh, 2007).

The Archive Ingest and Handling Test performed by the Digital Knowledge Centre of the Sheridan Library at John Hopkins University revealed lessons learned concerning technical issues. Starting with the memory consumption of the ingest process, the challenge lay in absolute size and number of objects to process. Another crucial part was creating log files of ingests, exports and migrations to monitor all processes and detect possible failures quickly. In addition, awareness is needed that migration tools and software can create flawed data and that the ingesting repository needs to be prepared for such contingencies (DiLauro et al., 2005). Another approach is to enrich file systems by using links between elements and add attributes to objects. In addition to advanced information retrieval, the provided infrastructure of linked data enables other features than regular file structures. Key elements here are the enriched context information about creation history, provenance and intended use. Based on the linked attributes of each files LiFS (Linking File Systems) enable advanced information infra-

structures that can be handled by current programs and future applications. The DareLux project explored the long-term preservation workflow for hydrology research data sets in 2008 and agree on the importance of quality control of the ingest process (Dürr et al.,2008, p.284). Nicholson and Dobрева (2009, p.8) took another stand at the established and popular OAIS model and looked for a way the model could be developed to a reliable and consistent digital preservation implementation framework. They suggest cross-fertilisation with other data life-cycle areas that are more advanced, and granular definition of pre-Ingest and post-Access functions.

4.5 Managing Metadata

Chowdhury and Chowdhury (2007, p.140) summarized the evolution of the metadata term-definition:

- Metadata describe various attributes of resources (Dempsey and Heery, 1997)
- Metadata describe a discrete data object (Gill, 1998)
- Metadata provide users with some useful knowledge about the existence of records and their characteristics (Dempsey and Heery, 1998)
- Metadata describe the content, format and/or attributes of an information resources (Haynes, 2004).”

Walker (2012, p.50) discovered in his analysis of file format migration and refreshment success rates in public archival repositories that some archives work with outdated file formats, which do not inherit the ability to be patched up to higher compatible formats, especially Microsoft Works and Word Perfect. Therefore, a constant migration with every software update is beneficial, using checksum comparison to control quality. Concerning the inevitable migration cycles Hodges and Anders (2007, p.61) suggest multi-format migration to provide a basis for superior formats in the future. Citing Borghoff (2006, p.14) it has to be considered that migration can lead to authenticity loss, hence the document adaption to the new software environment (Walker, 2012, p.49, 53). Metadata strongly influences information management and retrieval, next to enhancing retrieval performance and determination of authentic data, metadata provide a basis to manage electronic digital objects, and function as

key for interoperable application, to make it short “metadata is the future” (Haynes, 2004, p.11-12). Day (2001) cited in Haynes (2004, p.13) constructed seven purposes of metadata:

- resource description;
- recourse discovery;
- administration and management for resources;
- record of intellectual property rights (IPR);
- documenting software and hardware environments;
- preservation management of digital preservation;
- and providing information on context and authenticity;

Having the five types of metadata (administrative, descriptive, preservation, technical, use) by Gilliland-Swetland in mind, Haynes created a 5-point model including: resource description; information retrieval; management of information resources; documenting ownership and authenticity of digital resources; and interoperability.

Looking at types of standards reveals a development of formality, starting with proprietary standards created by a supplier; followed by *de facto* standards that hold the level of being widely accepted and used although they did not go through the formal standardization process. Industries and sectors, mostly with international scope, develop industry standards; whereas regional, national, and international standards are set by the relevant responsible body. In order to enable interoperable exchange of metadata, three different types of interoperability need to be acknowledged: semantic, structural, and syntactic. Dublin Core and AACR2 are examples of content description standards; RDF is a model for specifying semantic schemas; and XML enables syntactic metadata expressions, while using mark-up and tags to exchange and share data across applications (Haynes, 2004, p. 159-160).

Metadata capture, file management, and license handling are three predominant components for creating a submission agreement. Clarification on licenses and additional structural information provide links to related files and display relationships. Rights metadata created on basis of the license agreement have direct impact on descriptive and access metadata (Jones et al., 2006, p.87). Chowdhury and Chowdhury (2007, p.161, 160) discuss that in terms of mark-up languages, it is important to understand that extensible mark-up language (XML) and hypertext mark-up language (HTML) are extension of the standard generalised mark-up language (SGML). XML is established to be the best option in regards to RM and DP, since

SGML is too complex and resource-intensive, and HTML too simple. The weak points of XML are the limitations of only providing data formats for documents and the free interpretation of XML tags; the opposite to HTML tags which are standardized and can be universally interpreted by computer programs. The characteristics of open file formats include originating from a freely available standard; being developed by a community; multiple software packages can use them, not just one proprietary program; no patented components or IP restrictions (Oliver and Harvey, 2016, p.118).

4.6 Recognising Pre-Ingest and Ingest

Taking the approach of avoiding migration, the National Library of the Netherlands provides an example, by only accepting material in long-term capable file formats (Sheldon, 2010, p.15), the repository frees itself from making the migration decision and thereby potential errors. Therefore, the validity and authenticity of content and rendering is decided and controlled by the creator, the repository takes care of the file format preservation and meta-data enrichment. Up to date the regular access and authorization rules while handling data and metadata are read (view and print off), create (new objects and elements), edit (alter and edit), and delete (remove, preferably with audit trail) (Haynes, 2004, p.164-165). Jones et al. (2006, p.88) distinguish three stages in the submission workflow: metadata stage, file management stage, and licensing stage. Access metadata, descriptive metadata, and administrative metadata are allocated in the first stage, followed by structural and technical metadata accompanied by representation information, and the file itself in the second stage. The last stage takes care of license construction and rights distribution. Taking stakeholders into consideration while defining the intended use, the main parties can be summarised as: creator; institution; funder; publisher; library; general public (Jones et al. 2006, p.140). The author suggested in 2001 that deposit licences for digital materials should include copyright permissions, migration permissions, and permissions for emulation for the purpose of preservation (Jones et al., 2006, p.149).

Concerning ingest policies Oliver and Harvey (2016, p.79, 87) suggest the inclusion of statements about the method and quality that descriptive and representation information has to be delivered to the archive, and what the requirements are upon the data files and context

information. Another statement can target whether the archive only accepts normalized digital objects, accompanied by their un-altered original sources, all assigned with unique identifier and prior virus checks. Citing Green et al. (2009) a policy should cover the following topics and raise questions about: eligible depositor, data quality requirements, metadata, confidentiality and disclosure, embargo status, rights and ownership, and data files formats (Oliver and Harvey 2016, p.115). According to Kärberg (2013, p.85) the pre-ingest phase influences all subsequent activities and needs strong quality control, hence the information enrichment and linking is taking place there. The UK Data Archive Preservation Policy supports that argument, stating that curated data lowers the level of work and effort at the ingest stage and potentially increases the usability. Furthermore, the construction of DIP based on different software packages during the ingest process instead of automatically from the AIP on demand is suggested (UKDA, 2014, p. 8-9). Dürr et al. (2008, p. 292-293) agree on the importance of quality control during the ingest process and adds for consideration that the ingest procedure is difficult to generalize and in term of research each discipline creates different data sets and therefore needs different approaches.

Waugh (2007) explored the design and implementation of an ingest function to a digital archive and discovered the difficulties that arise while creating a balanced ingest function for producers to submit data. The ingest function being too difficult will lead to the producer storing their data longer rather than transferring the objects to the archive; the ingest function being too flexible leads to an inconsistent collection of objects and subsequently more effort to generate consistent preservation objects. Targeting error handling while transferring digital objects, the Public Record Office Victoria implemented positive acknowledgement protocols to monitor incomplete submission sets, lost objects, programming or operational errors. The producer receives a message stating that the archive accepted the data sets and will take over the responsibility for the digital objects, the creator has to retain the original data, along with the curated version and be prepared for possible re-submission. The Public Record Office Victoria only operates in submission/ ingest sets, submission of a single data object is not accepted. Based on an absolutely reliable storage system and ingest function, the author advises to only accept responsibility for the digital data objects when they are permanently stored. Any stage beforehand can include flawed and non-conforming data sets and it is up to the creator/ producer/ submitter to supply a fit for purpose data set.

4.7 Conclusion

Although the shapes and volumes of documents and records will evolve to fragmented and multi-file entities, the constant need for preservation actions will remain. Implementing RM standards and systems such as EDRMS provides structure, metadata control and file creation monitoring. Information architectures such as RMS, CMS, and EDRMS are set out to provide lossless authentic data maintenance, enable data discovery and retrieval and foster the comprehension and interpretation of found data by the users. To cope with increasing data volumes and the heterogeneous landscape of digital data, accompanied by indexing vocabulary variety and subsequent difficult search query formulation, information architecture and systems have been created for different areas. The Open Archival Information System was originally created for research data management, and finds its utilization in corporation, and public service environments too. Archivematica is a digital preservation solution, which provides ingest, digital preservation and access functionalities, but was mainly built for supporting the transfer and submission of data. Learning from approaches, experiences and issues one big topic is rights management and retaining rights. The best point to migrate data and metadata in the data and preservation cycle is still in discussions, the current trend tends to do it as soon as possible and even let the data producer do the finale migration with the archive only accepting finale migrated data objects. It seems to be beneficial if the producer uses their own software environment to normalize metadata and data, since the archive might not have the same software environment. One approach in pinning down the significant properties of digital objects leads to limitations to content, context, appearance, behaviour, and structure. Another strategy is to implement a stage in the transfer and digital preservation workflow where the archive actively decides to be responsible for the data set and therefore take over the liability for possible future issues with the digital objects. Log files and migration monitoring is recommended in general, but increasingly crucial for processing large data sets and collections. The discussion on the superiority of file format migration over file emulation gets new input with multi-format migration to provide superior formats in the future on the one side, and the cost-efficiency for keeping large volumes of data in their original state and emulating the needed software environment when needed on the other side.

Concerning license management, experts suggest that permissions covering copyright should be extended by permissions to migrate and emulate for preservation reasons. Suggestions for

creating policy and deposit agreements include among others information about the depositor, data quality, metadata quantity and quality, disclosure and confidentiality, and rights and ownership. The preservation efforts and administrative undertakings will decrease with strict quality control at the pre-ingest and ingest phases.

V Technical Analysis: Evaluation of Transfer and Ingest Functionalities

5.1 Introduction

This chapter includes the methodology chosen for the technical analysis of the Archivemática ingest function, followed by the results and conclusion. To investigate how to cope with files, documents and records from local authorities that are not yet curated for digital preservation, and are operated with Archivemática as the digital preservation system of choice, it is necessary to comprehend the technical architecture and functionalities. Research Objectives 1 to 3 are targeted in this chapter, the determination the most effective and efficient way to create a complete and consistent submission information package (SIP), containing digital data objects, metadata information and rights information is in focus.

The Archivemática installation of ARCW / NLW features three different areas: Pydio as platform to upload and store the data object and registries that are intended to be ingested to Archivemática, Archivemática itself, and AtoM as the discovery and access platform. That implies that Pydio stores the pre-SIP, Archivemática contains the SIP, the AIP and DIP, and AtoM provides access to the DIP.

“The primary function of Archivemática is to process digital transfers (accessioned digital objects), turn them into SIPs, apply format policies and create high-quality, repository-independent Archival Information Packages (AIP) using METS, PREMIS and Bagit. Archivemática is bundled with AtoM but is designed to upload Dissemination Information Packages (DIP), containing descriptive metadata and web-ready access copies, to any access system (e.g. DSpace, ContentDM, etc.)” (Artefactual Inc., 2015). The web-based dashboard of Archivemática version 1.5 guides the user through the process stages compliant to the OAIS functional model, the tabs represent Transfer, Ingest, Archival Storage, Access, and Administration. The Transfer and Ingest tabs contain the processing stages with micro-services, jobs and decisions to follow through the digital preservation steps. Archival Storage and Access display the preserved digital information packages. Configurations and adaptations of the system for user needs are located in the Administration and Preservation Planning Tab.

The micro-services of each job are designed to create structured information packages that contain the digital files, checksums, XML metadata, logs, and possible submission agreements. Over the course of the versions of Archivemática an extended Format Policy Registry

(FPR), with significant characteristics, risk assessment and normalization tool, has been developed. Using the format policies supports the maintenance of the normalized original files, and provides the possibility for file format migration and emulation strategies in the future (Artefactual Inc., 2015).

Table 1 displays the transfer and ingest workflow in Archivemata, including decision points and automated micro-services, to the point where the access ready DIP is stored.

1. TRANSFER		
Transfer selected objects from Pydio ¹ to Archivemata ²		
D1	Transfer Approval Decision	Transfer Rejection Possible
7 automated Micro-Services		
D2	Quarantine Decision	Transfer Rejection Possible
1 automated Micro-Service		
D3	File Format Decision	
8 automated Micro-Services		
2. INGEST		
6 automated Micro-Services		
D4	Normalization Decision	SIP Rejection Possible
1 automated Micro-Service		
D5	Normalization Approval Decision	Review + Report Option SIP Rejection Possible
3 automated Micro-Services		
D6	Transcription SIP Contents Decision	
6 automated Micro-Services		
D7	Upload DIP Decision	DIP Rejection Possible
4 automated Micro-Services		
INGEST COMPLETE (SIP, AIP, DIP created and stored)		

Table 1: Overview Archivemata Transfer and Ingest Micro-Services and Decision Points.

Rejection of an Information Packages leads to the end of a process. The transfer and Ingest of digital objects has to start again from the beginning.

Removing Information Packages from the Transfer or Ingest workflow does not lead to general deletion, just removal from the web-interface. AIP deletion can only be followed through after administration confirmation, although DIP deletion in the access area can be done without a system notification.

¹ Pydio is an enterprise system to store, synchronize and share digital data. URL: <https://pydio.com/> [Accessed 7 Sept. 2016].

² Archivemata is an open-source digital preservation system. URL: <https://www.archivemata.org/en/> [Accessed 7 Sept. 2016].

Table 2 gives an overview of the decision choices for each decision point in the previous workflow overview (Table 1, p. 26).

D1	Approve standard transfer
	approve / reject transfer
D2	Workflow decision - send transfer to quarantine
	reject transfer / skip quarantine / quarantine
D3	Select file format identification command
	Fido Version 1 PUID ³ runs Identify using Fido ⁴
	Skip File Identification
	Siegfried version 1.0.0 PUID runs Identify using Siegfried ⁵
	File Extension version 0.1 file extension runs Identify by File Extension
D4	Normalize
	Normalize for preservation and access
	Normalize for preservation
	Reject SIP
	Normalize service files for access
	Do not normalize
	Normalize manually
	Normalize for access
D5	Approve Normalization + Review + Report
	Approve / Redo / Reject
D6	Transcribe SIP contents
	Yes / No
D7	Upload DIP
	Upload DIP to Archivists Toolkit ⁶
	Upload DIP to CONTENT-dm ⁷
	Reject DIP
	Upload DIP to Atom

Table 2: Overview Archivematica Decision Points.

³ PRONOM Persistent Unique Identifier. URL: <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/aboutapps/pronom/puid.htm> [Accessed 7 Sept. 2016].

⁴ Fast Identity Online FIDO is an identification tool. URL: <https://fidoalliance.org/> [Accessed 7 Sept. 2016].

⁵ Signature-based file format identification tool Siegfried. URL: <http://www.itforarchivists.com/siegfried> [Accessed 12 Sept. 2016].

⁶ Archivist Toolkit is an open-source archival data management system. URL: <http://www.archiviststoolkit.org/> [Accessed 7 Sept. 2016].

⁷ Content-dm stores and manage digital data. URL: <http://www.oclc.org/en-US/contentdm.html> [Accessed 7 Sept. 2016].

5.2 Methodology

5.2.1 Evaluation Test Methodology

There are two ways to enter rights information in Archivematica: in the rights field in the Metadata (MD) Interface and in the actual Rights Interface. The Rights Interface allows several options for the data set, including Copyright, Statute, License, Donor, Policy, Other. The MD interface allows one entry for the complete data set, in contrast the Rights interface allows several rights entries for the data set. Created MD after the transfer and before the ingest phase is expressed in an METS XML file.

Descriptive Metadata	
Descriptive Metadata Section	<dmdSec>
External Descriptive Metadata	<mdRef>
Internal Descriptive Metadata	<mdWrap>
Administrative Metadata	
Administrative Metadata Section	<amdSec>
Technical Metadata	<techMD>
IPR Metadata	<rightsMD>
Source Metadata	<sourceMD>
Digital Provenance Metadata	<digiprovMD>
File Section	
File Section	<fileSec>
File Group	<fileGrp>
Structural Map	
Structural Map	<structMap>
METS pointer	<mptr>
File pointer	<fptr>
Structural Links	
Structural Links	<smLink>
Behaviour Section	
Behaviour	<behavior>

Table 3: METS Section Overview.

METS files include the main sections: descriptive metadata <dmdSec>, administrative metadata <amdSec>, file section <fileSec>, structural map <structMap>, structural links <smLink>, and behaviour sections <behaviour>, featured with additional tags in each section (METS Editorial Board, 2016) (Table 3). Input in the Archivematica Rights Interface is expressed as administrative metadata (PREMIS⁸), input in the Metadata Interface as descriptive metadata (DUBLIN CORE⁹). If the rights field in the Metadata Interface is used, the created information is located to <dc:rights>-tag in <dmdSec>. Using the actual Rights Interface leads to information being correctly allocated to the <rightsMD>-tag in the <amdSec>.

The metadata (MD) and rights editing and management showed different impacts for different scenarios. MD and Rights can either be entered manually in the Archivematica UI, or can be extracted automatically from an ingested Comma Separated Value (CSV) file. All entries made in Archivematica follow Dublin Core (DC) as MD standard, information provided in the CSV-file can follow DC as well, novel creations not compliant to DC will be allocated to the tag OTHER. The Artefactual team revealed that they are currently working on PREMIS compliant entries in the CSV-file. Information about the file creation and partially about the file history (e.g. content creation time; last time modified) can be found in the file information of the digital data object. In order to enhance the metadata to preservation level, further information is needed. The minimum metadata requirements in this case can be covered by entering information according to the 15 core elements of the metadata standard Dublin Core (NISO, 2007). Dublin Core will cover the basics, PREMIS is specified to document and display preservation metadata. In the current state Archivematica uses Dublin Core for the descriptive metadata, and PREMIS to manage the intellectual property rights in the administrative section. Currently the creator of Archivematica is working on adding PREMIS metadata in the CSV-file and subsequently Archivematica to process that. In the current version (1.5) only Dublin Core can be correctly extracted and allocated in the Archivematica METS XML file. Information extracted from the CSV-file that are not compliant to Dublin Core will be allocated to the "OTHER" element and therefore still available in the METS XML file, but not correctly allocated to the precise PREMIS element. The data-set in this test scenario consists of three

⁸ Preservation Metadata: Implementation Strategies (PREMIS). URL: <http://www.loc.gov/standards/premis/v3/index.html> [Accessed 12 Sept. 2016]

⁹ Dublin Core Metadata Element Set. URL: <http://dublincore.org/documents/dces/> [Accessed 12 Sept. 2016]

data objects (a PDF file, a WORD file and a EXCEL file) (Figure 6). The SIP therefore includes 3 data objects, the transformed AIP will contain these objects and their preservation versions.

Name	Date modified	Type	Size
20160106-_WPS_2016_New_Bulletin_Format_Revised_FINAL-_O	20/06/2016 15:50	PDF File	216 KB
BradfordCouncilProperty	20/06/2016 15:50	Microsoft Excel 97...	871 KB
merton_summary_accounts_2009-10_final	20/06/2016 15:50	Microsoft Word 9...	218 KB

Figure 6: Overview Data-Objects in Test-Sets.

This test-series intends to capture the different impacts of adding descriptive and administrative MD in the Archivemata user interface (UI) or with a CSV-file. Having the possible ingest of large collections or several SIP at the same time in mind, the automation of metadata ingests and curation is a desired outcome. Table 4 provides the keys for the visualization of the test data-sets in Table 5. Each data-set features different descriptive and administrative metadata, and MD ingest methods. Insights from this technical analysis correspond to *Research Objectives 1 to 3*.

	Data-Set
	Archivemata Metadata Editing in User Interface
	CSV file with Metadata

Table 4: Keys for Data-Set Contents.

Test 1	
	Data-set
Test 2	
	Dataset + Metadata Edit in Archivemata Metadata Interface
Test 3	
	Data-set + CSV file with Metadata
Test 4	
	Data-set + Metadata Edit in Archivemata Metadata Interface + CSV file with Metadata
Test 5	
	Data-set + CSV file with Metadata + Rights Edit in Archivemata Rights Interface

Table 5: Overview Contents Test Data-Set for Archivemata Transfer and Ingest Test.

The METS XML file displays entities for all ingested data objects, their preservation versions, the created metadata-sets, and a possible submission documentation. The main focus lies on the descriptive metadata changes in `<dmdSec>` and intellectual rights metadata (IPR) metadata `<rightsMD>`, however the differences between each test result indicates important information as well. Microsoft Edge was used to search through the METS XML files, the comparison of the METS XML files of each data-set focusses on the quality and quantity of created descriptive and administrative entities and tags.

5.3 Results

AR	Archivematica Rights Edit
AMD	Archivematica Metadata Edit
CSV	CSV-file with Metadata

Figure 7: Keys for Metadata Input Methods used.

1) Plain Data-Set, no Metadata Input

The first data-set was not supplemented by manually entered metadata (Table 6) to see what Archivematica extracts automatically from the file properties.

Key	Edit	Metadata Entered
AR	no	-
AMD	no	-
CSV	no	-

Table 6: Overview of Metadata Input Method for Test 1.

Results

Since no metadata (MD) was edited either in the Archivematica Interface nor provided in the comma-separated values (CSV) file, there is no `<dmdSec>` to be displayed. The `<amdSec>` sections shows one entry for each object: original, preservation version, submission documentation, but no entry for metadata (Figure 8). Adding metadata creates a metadata entity in the METS structure, since no additional metadata is provided this entity is not created. Therefore `<amdSec>` and `<techMD>` feature no additional entries, no corresponding file pointer `<fptr>`

is created to link the metadata entry to the data objects. That means without metadata input in Archivematica, there is no descriptive metadata in the METS XML file for the SIP.

```

- <mets:fileSec>
- <mets:fileGrp USE="original">
- <mets:file ID="file-c6113409-f68f-44dd-a268-06c8be990e7a" ADMID="amdSec_2" GROUPID="Group-c6113409-f68f-44dd-a268-06c8be990e7a">
  <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/20160106-_WPS_2016_New_Bulletin_Format_Revised_FINAL_0.pdf"/>
  </mets:file>
- <mets:file ID="file-0bf2ec50-570c-497e-bec4-c2e78095c1bb" ADMID="amdSec_3" GROUPID="Group-0bf2ec50-570c-497e-bec4-c2e78095c1bb">
  <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/BradfordCouncilProperty.xls"/>
  </mets:file>
- <mets:file ID="file-b0035838-074e-47e7-bf61-ef26ce3cac9c" ADMID="amdSec_4" GROUPID="Group-b0035838-074e-47e7-bf61-ef26ce3cac9c">
  <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/merton_summary_accounts_2009-10_final.doc"/>
  </mets:file>
</mets:fileGrp>
- <mets:fileGrp USE="submissionDocumentation">
- <mets:file ID="file-b06802c8-3e47-4529-9851-c8089b4b8077" ADMID="amdSec_5" GROUPID="Group-b06802c8-3e47-4529-9851-c8089b4b8077">
  <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/submissionDocumentation/transfer-jkb-MD-Test2-noCSV-noMD_160701-462150ce-fa15-4282-9589-5fff0f77cd4a/METS.xml"/>
  </mets:file>
</mets:fileGrp>
- <mets:fileGrp USE="preservation">
- <mets:file ID="file-6293aae0-7c4c-43b9-9289-d3a9224636a0" ADMID="amdSec_1" GROUPID="Group-c6113409-f68f-44dd-a268-06c8be990e7a">
  <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/20160106-_WPS_2016_New_Bulletin_Format_Revised_FINAL_0-3525d2f3-0b71-4914-8d58-58e5eb23d484.pdf"/>
  </mets:file>
</mets:fileGrp>
</mets:fileSec>

```

Figure 8: Test 1 METS XML - <amdSec> for each entity in the SIP.

2) Metadata Edit with Dublin Core in Archivematica UI

In the second test metadata was entered in the MD Interface in Archivematica (Table 7; Figure 9 and 10), what resulted in descriptive MD compliant to Dublin Core.

Key	Edit	Metadata Entered
AR	no	-
AMD	yes	dc.title; dc.creator; dc.subject; dc.description; dc.publisher; dc.contributor; dc.rights
CSV	no	-

Table 7: Overview of Metadata Input Method for Test 2.

Transfer / jkb-MD-test2-noCSV-yesMD_160701 / Metadata / Add

Metadata

jkb-MD-test2-noCSV-yesMD_160701

Title
MM01

Part of AIC
Optional: leave blank if unsure

Creator
Ministry of XYZ

Subject

Register

Description
Pdf shows abc

Publisher
Department ABC, Information Officer B

Contributor
Department ABC, Administrative Officer M

Date

Format
Use ISO 8061 (YYYY-MM-DD or YYYY-MM-DDYYYY-MM-DD)

Identifier

Source

Figure 9: Test 2 – Metadata Input in Archivematica Metadata Interface 1/2.

Transfer / jkb-MD-test2-noCSV-yesMD_160701 / Metadata / Add

Metadata

jkb-MD-test2-noCSV-yesMD_160701

Title
MM01

Part of AIC
Optional: leave blank if unsure

Creator
Ministry of XYZ

Subject

Register

Description
Pdf shows abc

Publisher
Department ABC, Information Officer B

Contributor
Department ABC, Administrative Officer M

Date

Format
Use ISO 8061 (YYYY-MM-DD or YYYY-MM-DDYYYY-MM-DD)

Identifier

Source

Relation

Language
Use ISO 639

Coverage

Rights
Copyright held by Ministry of XYZ

Create Cancel

Figure 10: Test 2 – Metadata Input in Archivematica Metadata Interface 2/2.

Results

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="ASCII"?>
- <mets:mets xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.loc.gov/METS/
http://www.loc.gov/standards/mets/version18/mets.xsd" xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink"
xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xmlns:mets="http://www.loc.gov/METS/">
  <mets:metsHdr CREATEDATE="2016-07-01T09:42:54"/>
  - <mets:dmdSec ID="dmdSec_1">
    - <mets:mdWrap MDTYPE="DC">
      - <mets:xmlData>
        - <dcterms:dublincore xsi:schemaLocation="http://purl.org/dc/terms/
http://dublincore.org/schemas/xmls/qdc/2008/02/11/dcterms.xsd"
xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/" xmlns:dcterms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/">
          <dc:title>MM01</dc:title>
          <dc:creator>Ministry of XYZ</dc:creator>
          <dc:subject>Register</dc:subject>
          <dc:description>Pdf shows abc</dc:description>
          <dc:publisher>Department ABC, Information Officer B</dc:publisher>
          <dc:contributor>Department ABC, Administrative Officer M</dc:contributor>
          <dc:rights>Copyright held by Ministry of XYZ</dc:rights>
        </dcterms:dublincore>
      </mets:xmlData>
    </mets:mdWrap>
  </mets:dmdSec>
```

Figure 11: Test 2 METS XML – <dmdSec> with Dublin Core metadata for the whole SIP.

One entry for the complete submitted data set in <dmdSec> (Figure 11) and one corresponding <structMap>. The <amdSec> sections shows one entry for each object (original, preservation version, metadata, submission documentation) and provides two metadata entries (Figure 12). Therefore <amdSec> and <techMD> feature two more entries, additionally two more file pointer <fptr> are created to link the metadata entry to the data objects (see Appendix A). The manually entered information in the Archivematica UI is displayed in the <dmdSec>, the rights information is displayed in the <dc:rights>-tag in <dmdSec> and not in the correct <rightsMD>-tag in <amdSec>. That means that rights entered in the Metadata Interface is expressed as descriptive MD and not as administrative. The Rights Interface should be preferred to enter rights related information, that will result in correctly administrative MD.

```
- <mets:fileSec>
- <mets:fileGrp USE="original">
  - <mets:file ID="file-409ef89f-a13b-43d5-ac34-41f905a9bdd1" ADMID="amdSec_2" GROUPID="Group-409ef89f-a13b-43d5-ac34-41f905a9bdd1">
    <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/20160106_WPS_2016_New_Bulletin_Format_Revised_FINAL_0.pdf"/>
  </mets:file>
  - <mets:file ID="file-2074ffe5-36e2-4b98-83ca-df3e419576b8" ADMID="amdSec_3" GROUPID="Group-2074ffe5-36e2-4b98-83ca-df3e419576b8">
    <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/BradfordCouncilProperty.xls"/>
  </mets:file>
  - <mets:file ID="file-cfb7a7c2-9fda-4bcc-b2c6-1882cf20e428" ADMID="amdSec_4" GROUPID="Group-cfb7a7c2-9fda-4bcc-b2c6-1882cf20e428">
    <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/merton_summary_accounts_2009-10_final.doc"/>
  </mets:file>
</mets:fileGrp>
- <mets:fileGrp USE="submissionDocumentation">
  - <mets:file ID="file-82111752-749a-4e51-ae7c-71d5d1098748" ADMID="amdSec_7" GROUPID="Group-82111752-749a-4e51-ae7c-71d5d1098748">
    <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/submissionDocumentation/transfer-jkb-MD-Test2-noCSV-yesMD_160701-12444461-a957-49e6-8758-f5023e1b2c03/METS.xml"/>
  </mets:file>
</mets:fileGrp>
- <mets:fileGrp USE="preservation">
  - <mets:file ID="file-8bdf84a5-6f75-412c-8fda-f4e43fb792a1" ADMID="amdSec_1" GROUPID="Group-409ef89f-a13b-43d5-ac34-41f905a9bdd1">
    <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/20160106_WPS_2016_New_Bulletin_Format_Revised_FINAL_0-a205376a-c9a7-4896-96d0-f4d8b2a6749f.pdf"/>
  </mets:file>
</mets:fileGrp>
- <mets:fileGrp USE="metadata">
  - <mets:file ID="file-693cac37-a0a5-4239-86e6-e547100a527d" ADMID="amdSec_5" GROUPID="Group-693cac37-a0a5-4239-86e6-e547100a527d">
    <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/metadata/dc.json"/>
  </mets:file>
  - <mets:file ID="file-b5aa192d-dc83-469b-a708-d5d3e97a3f39" ADMID="amdSec_6" GROUPID="Group-b5aa192d-dc83-469b-a708-d5d3e97a3f39">
    <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/metadata/transfers/jkb-MD-Test2-noCSV-yesMD_160701-12444461-a957-49e6-8758-f5023e1b2c03/dc.json"/>
  </mets:file>
</mets:fileGrp>
</mets:fileSec>
```

Figure 12: Test 2 METS XML - <amdSec> for each entity in the SIP.

3) CSV-File with DUBLIN CORE and other information

In this test the descriptive MD compliant to Dublin Core and additional information (Table 8) was entered in a CSV-file (Figure 13 and 14) to see how Archivematica extracts and allocates the provided information.

Key	Edit	Metadata Entered
AR	no	-
AMD	no	-
CSV	yes	filename; dc.title; dcterms.issued; dc.publisher; dc.contributor; dc.subject;, dc.subject; dc.date; dc.description; notes; dcterms.isPartOf; repository; dc.rights; project_website; dc.format

Table 8: Overview of Metadata Input Method for Test 3.

filename	dc.title	dcterms.issued	dc.publisher	dc.contributor
objects/20160106-MM01	MM01	01/01/2015	Department ABC, Information Officer B	Department ABC, Administrative Officer M
objects/BradfordC	MM02	02/01/2015	Department ABC, Information Officer B	Department ABC, Administrative Officer M
objects/merton_s	MM03	03/01/2015	Department ABC, Information Officer B	Department ABC, Administrative Officer M

dc.subject	dc.subject	dc.date	dc.description	notes	dcterms.isPartOf	repository
Register	PDF	29/06/2016	Pdf shows abc	this is a test	Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q1	NLW Archivematica
Register	EXCEL	30/06/2016	EXCEL shows def	this is a test	Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q2	NLW Archivematica
Register	WORD	01/07/2016	WORD shows ghi	this is a test	Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q3	NLW Archivematica

dc.rights	project_website	dc.format
Copyright held by Ministry of XYZ	wesbsite address	pdf/pdf
Copyright held by Ministry of XYZ	wesbsite address	vnd.ms-excel/xls
Copyright held by Ministry of XYZ	wesbsite address	msword/doc

Figure 13: Test 3 CSV-File - Dublin Core and additional information.

Name	Date modified	Type	Size
metadata	01/07/2016 10:47	File folder	
20160106-_WPS_2016_New_Bulletin_For...	20/06/2016 15:50	PDF File	216 KB
BradfordCouncilProperty	20/06/2016 15:50	Microsoft Excel 97...	871 KB
merton_summary_accounts_2009-10_final	20/06/2016 15:50	Microsoft Word 9...	218 KB

Figure 14: Test 3 - Data-Set with Data-Objects and Metadata-File with CSV-File.

Results

One entry each data object in <dmdSec>(Figure 15) and one corresponding <structMap>. The <amdSec> sections shows one entry for each object (original, preservation version, metadata, submission documentation) and provides one metadata entity (Figure 16). Therefore

<amdSec> and <techMD> feature one more entry, additionally one more file pointer <fptr> is created to link the metadata entry to the data objects (see Appendix A). The not DC compliant information uses the terms from the CSV-file columns as tags. That implies that information that cannot be covered by the DC element set can be entered with own terms in the CSV-file. Information about manifestations, retention schedules and other specific information are able to be captured and expressed with this method.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="ASCII"?>
- <mets:mets xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.loc.gov/METS/
http://www.loc.gov/standards/mets/version18/mets.xsd" xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink"
xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xmlns:mets="http://www.loc.gov/METS/">
  <mets:metsHdr CREATEDATE="2016-07-01T09:53:25"/>
  - <mets:dmdSec ID="dmdSec_1">
    - <mets:mdWrap MDTYPE="DC">
      - <mets:xmlData>
        - <dcterms:dublincore xsi:schemaLocation="http://purl.org/dc/terms/
http://dublincore.org/schemas/xmls/qdc/2008/02/11/dcterms.xsd"
xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/" xmlns:dcterms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/">
          <dc:title>MM01</dc:title>
          <dcterms:issued>01/01/2015</dcterms:issued>
          <dc:publisher>Department ABC, Information Officer B</dc:publisher>
          <dc:contributor>Department ABC, Administrative Officer M</dc:contributor>
          <dc:subject>Register</dc:subject>
          <dc:subject>PDF</dc:subject>
          <dc:date>29/06/2016</dc:date>
          <dc:description>Pdf shows abc</dc:description>
          <dcterms:isPartOf>Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q1</dcterms:isPartOf>
          <dc:rights>Copyright held by Ministry of XYZ</dc:rights>
          <dc:format>pdf/pdf</dc:format>
        </dcterms:dublincore>
      </mets:xmlData>
    </mets:mdWrap>
  </mets:dmdSec>
- <mets:dmdSec ID="dmdSec_2">
  - <mets:mdWrap MDTYPE="OTHER" OTHERMDTYPE="CUSTOM">
    - <mets:xmlData>
      <notes>this is a test</notes>
      <repository>NLW Archivemata</repository>
      <project_website>website address</project_website>
    </mets:xmlData>
  </mets:mdWrap>
</mets:dmdSec>
```

Figure 15: Test 3 METS XML – <dmdSec> with Dublin Core metadata and other information for each Data-Object.

```
- <mets:fileSec>
- <mets:fileGrp USE="original">
  - <mets:file ID="file-5f3f54c3-dca2-417e-bbe2-b4adf1242771" ADMID="amdSec_2" GROUPID="Group-5f3f54c3-dca2-417e-bbe2-b4adf1242771">
    <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/20160106-_WPS_2016_New_Bulletin_Format_Revised_FINAL_-_0.pdf"/>
  </mets:file>
  - <mets:file ID="file-7fd1a2b4-1cd7-440b-bb52-a1b410d69d99" ADMID="amdSec_3" GROUPID="Group-7fd1a2b4-1cd7-440b-bb52-a1b410d69d99">
    <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/BradfordCouncilProperty.xls"/>
  </mets:file>
  - <mets:file ID="file-bd9af17e-1611-42ab-bc0d-4d6488428a8b" ADMID="amdSec_4" GROUPID="Group-bd9af17e-1611-42ab-bc0d-4d6488428a8b">
    <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/merton_summary_accounts_2009-10_final.doc"/>
  </mets:file>
</mets:fileGrp>
- <mets:fileGrp USE="submissionDocumentation">
  - <mets:file ID="file-72811a15-a019-4731-8fc9-35254bb90c98" ADMID="amdSec_6" GROUPID="Group-72811a15-a019-4731-8fc9-35254bb90c98">
    <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/submissionDocumentation/transfer-jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-noMD_160701-9620f424-65bb-49c8-ac8d-588615bc4d60/METS.xml"/>
  </mets:file>
</mets:fileGrp>
- <mets:fileGrp USE="preservation">
  - <mets:file ID="file-22621ec9-2c35-46c8-82ef-dc35f00ee38c" ADMID="amdSec_1" GROUPID="Group-5f3f54c3-dca2-417e-bbe2-b4adf1242771">
    <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/20160106-_WPS_2016_New_Bulletin_Format_Revised_FINAL_-_0-26debed5-be9f-4dce-b514-fa38daeb3b30.pdf"/>
  </mets:file>
</mets:fileGrp>
- <mets:fileGrp USE="metadata">
  - <mets:file ID="file-463f176c-fb7c-4485-a679-fcef7a4d04d6" ADMID="amdSec_5" GROUPID="Group-463f176c-fb7c-4485-a679-fcef7a4d04d6">
    <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/metadata/transfers/jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-noMD_160701-9620f424-65bb-49c8-ac8d-588615bc4d60/metadata.csv"/>
  </mets:file>
</mets:fileGrp>
</mets:fileSec>
```

Figure 16: Test 3 METS XML - <amdSec> for each entity in the SIP.

4) CSV-File with DUBLIN CORE and Metadata Edit with DUBLIN CORE in Archivematica

The fourth test aimed to explore the impact of entering similar information in the MD Interface in Archivematica and in a CSV-file (Table 9; Figures 17 to 19). Additionally, the CSV-file featured a PREMIS metadata entry to see where this information is allocated in the METS XML file by Archivematica.

Key	Edit	Metadata Entered
AR	no	-
AMD	yes	title; creator; subject; description; publisher; contributor; identifier; source; relation; language; coverage; rights
CSV	yes	file-name; dc.title; dcterms.issued; dc.subject; dc.subject; dcterms.isPartOf; dc.format; premis:copyrightStatus

Table 9: Overview of Metadata Input Method for Test 4.

The screenshot shows the Archivematica web interface for editing metadata. The breadcrumb trail is 'Transfer / jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-yesMD_160701 / Metadata / Edit'. The main heading is 'Metadata' with the identifier 'jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-yesMD_160701'. The form fields are as follows:

- Title:** MMX
- Part of AIC:** (empty)
- Optional:** leave blank if unsure
- Creator:** Ministry of XYZ
- Subject:** MMX Test
- Description:** This is description text in the Archivematica UI
- Publisher:** Ministry of XYZ, Department ABC
- Contributor:** Information Officer B
- Date:** (empty)
- Use ISO 8061:** (YYYY-MM-DD or YYYY-MM-DD/YYYY-MM-DD)
- Format:** (empty)
- Identifier:** 0001
- Source:** (empty)

Figure 17: Test 4 – Metadata Input in Archivematica Metadata Interface 1/2.

Figure 18: Test 4 – Metadata Input in Archivemata Metadata Interface 2/2.

filename	dc.title	dcterms.issued	dc.subject	dc.subject	dcterms.isPartOf	dc.format	premis:copyrightStatus
objects/20160106-MM01	MM01	01/01/2015	Register	PDF	Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q1	pdf/pdf	Deposit to Archive
objects/BradfordC-MM02	MM02	02/01/2015	Register	EXCEL	Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q2	vnd.ms-excel/xls	Deposit to Archive
objects/merton_sl-MM03	MM03	03/01/2015	Register	WORD	Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q3	msword/doc	Deposit to Archive

Figure 19: Test 4 CSV-File - Dublin Core and PREMIS.

Results

```

<?xml version="1.0" encoding="ASCII"?>
- <mets:mets xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.loc.gov/METS/
http://www.loc.gov/standards/mets/version18/mets.xsd" xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink"
xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xmlns:mets="http://www.loc.gov/METS/">
  <mets:metsHdr CREATEDATE="2016-07-01T13:47:34"/>
  - <mets:dmdSec ID="dmdSec_7">
    - <mets:mdWrap MDTYPE="DC">
      - <mets:xmlData>
        - <dcterms:dublincore xsi:schemaLocation="http://purl.org/dc/terms/
http://dublincore.org/schemas/xmls/qdc/2008/02/11/dcterms.xsd"
xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/" xmlns:dcterms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/">
          <dc:title>MMX</dc:title>
          <dc:creator>Ministry of XYZ</dc:creator>
          <dc:subject>MMX Test</dc:subject>
          <dc:description>This is description text in the Archivemata UI</dc:description>
          <dc:publisher>Ministry of XYZ, Department ABC</dc:publisher>
          <dc:contributor>Information Officer B</dc:contributor>
          <dc:identifier>0001</dc:identifier>
          <dc:source>Source</dc:source>
          <dc:relation>Relation</dc:relation>
          <dc:language>Language</dc:language>
          <dc:coverage>Coverage</dc:coverage>
          <dc:rights>This is free text in the rights field.</dc:rights>
        </dcterms:dublincore>
      </mets:xmlData>
    </mets:mdWrap>
  </mets:dmdSec>

```

Figure 20: Test 4 METS XML – <dmdSec> with Dublin Core metadata for the whole SIP.

```

- <mets:dmdSec ID="dmdSec_1">
  - <mets:mdWrap MDTYPE="DC">
    - <mets:xmlData>
      - <dcterms:dublincore xsi:schemaLocation="http://purl.org/dc/terms/
http://dublincore.org/schemas/xmls/qdc/2008/02/11/dcterms.xsd"
xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/" xmlns:dcterms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/">
        <dc:title>MM01</dc:title>
        <dcterms:issued>01/01/2015</dcterms:issued>
        <dc:subject>Register</dc:subject>
        <dc:subject>PDF</dc:subject>
        <dcterms:isPartOf>Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q1</dcterms:isPartOf>
        <dc:format>pdf/pdf</dc:format>
      </dcterms:dublincore>
    </mets:xmlData>
  </mets:mdWrap>
</mets:dmdSec>
- <mets:dmdSec ID="dmdSec_2">
  - <mets:mdWrap MDTYPE="OTHER" OTHERMDTYPE="CUSTOM">
    - <mets:xmlData>
      <premis_copyrightstatus>Deposit to Archive</premis_copyrightstatus>
    </mets:xmlData>
  </mets:mdWrap>
</mets:dmdSec>

```

Figure 21: Test 4 METS XML – <dmdSec> with Dublin Core metadata for each Data-Object.

Two entries for each data object in <dmdSec>(Figure 20 and 21) and one corresponding <structMap>. The <amdSec> sections shows one entry for each object (original, preservation version, metadata, submission documentation) and provides one metadata entity (Figure 22). Therefore <amdSec> and <techMD> feature three more entries, additionally three more file pointer <fptr> are created to link the metadata entry to the data objects (see Appendix A).

5) CSV-File and Rights Metadata Edit with PREMIS in the Archivemata UI

The last test focusses on the administrative rights management, therefore the descriptive MD is provided in the CSV-file and the Rights Interface in Archivemata is used to enter copyright- and statute- information (Table 10; Figures 24 to 26).

Key	Edit	Metadata Entered
AR	yes	<u>Copyright:</u> status; jurisdiction; determination; start date; note; document identifier type, value, role <u>Statute:</u> jurisdiction; citation; determination date; start date; document identifier type, value, role
AMD	no	-
CSV	yes	file-name; dc.title; dcterms.issued; dc.subject; dcterms.isPartOf; dc.format

Table 10: Overview of Metadata Input Method for Test 5.

The screenshot shows the 'Rights' interface in Archivemata. The breadcrumb trail is 'Transfer > Ingest > Archival storage > Preservation planning > Access > Adm'. The page title is 'Rights' with the identifier 'jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-yesRightsMD_160701'. The 'Basis' dropdown is set to 'Copyright'. The 'Copyright status' field contains 'Copyright Status Test'. The 'Copyright jurisdiction' field contains 'Copyright jurisdiction Test'. The 'Copyright determination date' field contains '2016-07-01' with a note 'Use ISO 8061 (YYYY-MM-DD)'. The 'Copyright start date' field contains '2016-07-01' with the same note. The 'Copyright end date' field is empty with the note 'Use ISO 8061 (YYYY-MM-DD)'. The 'Open End Date' checkbox is checked. The 'Copyright documentation identifier' section has three sub-fields: 'Type' (Type1), 'Value' (Value1), and 'Role' (Role1). The 'Copyright note' field contains 'Copyright note test'. At the bottom, there are 'Save', 'Next', and 'Cancel' buttons.

Figure 24: Test 4 – Rights Metadata Input in Archivemata Rights Interface 1/2.

The screenshot shows the Archivematica interface for entering rights metadata. The page title is "Rights" and the identifier is "jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-yesRightsMD_160701". The form includes the following fields:

- Basis:** A dropdown menu with "Statute" selected.
- Statute jurisdiction:** A text input field containing "Statute jurisdiction Test".
- Statute citation:** A text input field containing "Statute citation Test".
- Statute determination date:** A text input field containing "2016-07-01" with a note "Use ISO 8061 (YYYY-MM-DD)".
- Statute start date:** A text input field containing "2016-07-01" with a note "Use ISO 8061 (YYYY-MM-DD)".
- Statute end date:** An empty text input field with a note "Use ISO 8061 (YYYY-MM-DD)".
- Open End Date**
- Statute documentation identifier:** A table with three rows:

Type
Type2
Value
Value2
Role
Role2
- Statute note:** A text area containing "Statute Note Test".

At the bottom, there are three buttons: "Save", "Next", and "Cancel".

Figure 25: Rights Metadata Input in Archivematica Rights Interface 2/2.

filename	dc.title	dcterms.issued	dc.subject	dc.subject	dcterms.isPartOf	dc.format
objects/2016010	MM01	01/01/2015	Register	PDF	Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q1	pdf/pdf
objects/Bradfor	MM02	02/01/2015	Register	EXCEL	Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q2	vnd.ms-excel/xls
objects/merton	MM03	03/01/2015	Register	WORD	Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q3	msword/doc

Figure 26: Test 5 CSV-File - Dublin Core.

Results

One entry each data object in `<dmdSec>` (Figure 27) and one corresponding `<structMap>`. The `<amdSec>` sections shows one entry for each object (original, preservation version, metadata, submission documentation) and provides one metadata entry (Figure 29). Therefore `<amdSec>` and `<techMD>` feature one more entries, additionally one more file pointer `<fptr>` is created to link the metadata entry to the data objects (see Appendix A).

Each data object is allocated with three <rightsMD> containing two Copyright elements and one Statute element (Figure 28), therefore in this example the <rightsMD> section in the XML shows the highest amount of entries in comparison to the other tests. Using this input method for descriptive and administrative MD results in automatized processing of the metadata from the CSV-file, the manual input of rights information in Archivematica is inevitable in version 1.5.

```

<?xml version="1.0" encoding="ASCII"?>
- <mets:mets xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.loc.gov/METS/
http://www.loc.gov/standards/mets/version18/mets.xsd" xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink"
xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xmlns:mets="http://www.loc.gov/METS/">
  <mets:metsHdr CREATEDATE="2016-07-01T14:18:41"/>
  - <mets:dmdSec ID="dmdSec_1">
    - <mets:mdWrap MDTYPE="DC">
      - <mets:xmlData>
        - <dcterms:dublincore xsi:schemaLocation="http://purl.org/dc/terms/
http://dublincore.org/schemas/xmls/qdc/2008/02/11/dcterms.xsd"
xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/" xmlns:dcterms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/">
          <dc:title>MM01</dc:title>
          <dcterms:issued>01/01/2015</dcterms:issued>
          <dc:subject>Register</dc:subject>
          <dc:subject>PDF</dc:subject>
          <dcterms:isPartOf>Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q1</dcterms:isPartOf>
          <dc:format>pdf/pdf</dc:format>
        </dcterms:dublincore>
      </mets:xmlData>
    </mets:mdWrap>
  </mets:dmdSec>
  - <mets:dmdSec ID="dmdSec_2">
    - <mets:mdWrap MDTYPE="DC">
      - <mets:xmlData>
        - <dcterms:dublincore xsi:schemaLocation="http://purl.org/dc/terms/
http://dublincore.org/schemas/xmls/qdc/2008/02/11/dcterms.xsd"
xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/" xmlns:dcterms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/">
          <dc:title>MM02</dc:title>
          <dcterms:issued>02/01/2015</dcterms:issued>
          <dc:subject>Register</dc:subject>
          <dc:subject>EXCEL</dc:subject>
          <dcterms:isPartOf>Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q2</dcterms:isPartOf>
          <dc:format>vnd.ms-excel/xls</dc:format>
        </dcterms:dublincore>
      </mets:xmlData>
    </mets:mdWrap>
  </mets:dmdSec>
  - <mets:dmdSec ID="dmdSec_3">
    - <mets:mdWrap MDTYPE="DC">
      - <mets:xmlData>
        - <dcterms:dublincore xsi:schemaLocation="http://purl.org/dc/terms/
http://dublincore.org/schemas/xmls/qdc/2008/02/11/dcterms.xsd"
xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/" xmlns:dcterms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/">
          <dc:title>MM03</dc:title>
          <dcterms:issued>03/01/2015</dcterms:issued>
          <dc:subject>Register</dc:subject>
          <dc:subject>WORD</dc:subject>
          <dcterms:isPartOf>Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q3</dcterms:isPartOf>
          <dc:format>msword/doc</dc:format>
        </dcterms:dublincore>
      </mets:xmlData>
    </mets:mdWrap>
  </mets:dmdSec>

```

Figure 27: Test 5 METS XML – <dmdSec> with Dublin Core metadata for each Data-Object.

```

- <mets:rightsMD ID="rightsMD_2">
  - <mets:mdWrap MDTYPE="PREMIS:RIGHTS">
    - <mets:xmlData>
      - <premis:rightsStatement xsi:schemaLocation="info:lc/xmlns/premis-v2
        http://www.loc.gov/standards/premis/v2/premis-v2-2.xsd"
        xmlns:premis="info:lc/xmlns/premis-v2">
        - <premis:rightsStatementIdentifier>
          <premis:rightsStatementIdentifierType>UUID</premis:rightsStatementIdentifierType>
          <premis:rightsStatementIdentifierValue>cc189418-5aa8-4836-baab-
            34aa31a883f0</premis:rightsStatementIdentifierValue>
        </premis:rightsStatementIdentifier>
        <premis:rightsBasis>Copyright</premis:rightsBasis>
        - <premis:copyrightInformation>
          <premis:copyrightStatus>Copyright Status Test</premis:copyrightStatus>
          <premis:copyrightJurisdiction>Copyright jurisdiction Test</premis:copyrightJurisdiction>
          <premis:copyrightStatusDeterminationDate>2016-07-
            01</premis:copyrightStatusDeterminationDate>
          <premis:copyrightNote>Copyright note test</premis:copyrightNote>
        - <premis:copyrightDocumentationIdentifier>
          <premis:copyrightDocumentationIdentifierType>Type1</premis:copyrightDocumentationIdentifierType>
          <premis:copyrightDocumentationIdentifierValue>Value1</premis:copyrightDocumentationIdentifierValue>
          <premis:copyrightDocumentationRole>Role1</premis:copyrightDocumentationRole>
        </premis:copyrightDocumentationIdentifier>
        - <premis:copyrightApplicableDates>
          <premis:startDate>2016-07-01</premis:startDate>
          <premis:endDate>OPEN</premis:endDate>
        </premis:copyrightApplicableDates>
        </premis:copyrightInformation>
        - <premis:rightsGranted>
          <premis:act>Act1</premis:act>
          <premis:restriction>Allow</premis:restriction>
        - <premis:termOfGrant>
          <premis:startDate>2016-07-01</premis:startDate>
          <premis:endDate>OPEN</premis:endDate>
        </premis:termOfGrant>
          <premis:rightsGrantedNote>Restriction Note Test</premis:rightsGrantedNote>
        </premis:rightsGranted>
        - <premis:linkingObjectIdentifier>
          <premis:linkingObjectIdentifierType>UUID</premis:linkingObjectIdentifierType>
          <premis:linkingObjectIdentifierValue>81218b89-5ae3-4611-8ceb-
            0640024cb72a</premis:linkingObjectIdentifierValue>
        </premis:linkingObjectIdentifier>
        </premis:rightsStatement>
      </mets:xmlData>
    </mets:mdWrap>
  </mets:rightsMD>

```

Figure 28: Test 5 METS XML – <rightsMD> entry for Copyright.

```

- <mets:fileSec>
  - <mets:fileGrp USE="original">
    - <mets:file ID="file-81218b89-5ae3-4611-8ceb-0640024cb72a" ADMID="amdSec_2" GROUPID="Group-81218b89-5ae3-4611-8ceb-0640024cb72a">
      <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/20160106-_WPS_2016_New_Bulletin_Format_Revised_FINAL_0.pdf"/>
    </mets:file>
    - <mets:file ID="file-fc6dd0a9-bcb2-4e2b-88ad-ae191e8a7f1" ADMID="amdSec_3" GROUPID="Group-fc6dd0a9-bcb2-4e2b-88ad-ae191e8a7f1">
      <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/BradfordCouncilProperty.xls"/>
    </mets:file>
    - <mets:file ID="file-53efcb4d-3d9f-4ab1-ae87-d4e095828add" ADMID="amdSec_4" GROUPID="Group-53efcb4d-3d9f-4ab1-ae87-d4e095828add">
      <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/merton_summary_accounts_2009-10_final.doc"/>
    </mets:file>
  </mets:fileGrp>
  - <mets:fileGrp USE="submissionDocumentation">
    - <mets:file ID="file-a493a2f6-8c30-4e70-bb1d-3e6d8d10025e" ADMID="amdSec_6" GROUPID="Group-a493a2f6-8c30-4e70-bb1d-3e6d8d10025e">
      <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/submissionDocumentation/transfer-jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-yesRightsMD_160701-3275cf09-1172-4874-8086-096be19f963a/METS.xml"/>
    </mets:file>
  </mets:fileGrp>
  - <mets:fileGrp USE="preservation">
    - <mets:file ID="file-e2587617-9ad0-469f-b7fd-4d0b93fd5335" ADMID="amdSec_1" GROUPID="Group-81218b89-5ae3-4611-8ceb-0640024cb72a">
      <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/20160106-_WPS_2016_New_Bulletin_Format_Revised_FINAL_0-3f4d9963-d0a4-49a7-a72c-66ca81861d5b.pdf"/>
    </mets:file>
  </mets:fileGrp>
  - <mets:fileGrp USE="metadata">
    - <mets:file ID="file-489ff17a-9810-444c-b0f4-fe90553a0f40" ADMID="amdSec_5" GROUPID="Group-489ff17a-9810-444c-b0f4-fe90553a0f40">
      <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/metadata/transfers/jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-yesRightsMD_160701-3275cf09-1172-4874-8086-096be19f963a/metadata.csv"/>
    </mets:file>
  </mets:fileGrp>
</mets:fileSec>

```

Figure 29: Test 5 METS XML - <amdSec> for each entity in the SIP.

5.4 Conclusion

This technical analysis of the transfer and ingest functionality of Archivematica set out to understand the manual and automatic processes, and figure out the most efficient and effective method for metadata and rights input. The test-series shows that datasets ingested without additional MD either in the Archivematica UI or in an additional CSV-file will not present any descriptive MD and subsequently administrative information in the METS XML file, which contains information about all data-objects and corresponding metadata.

Adding MD in general, leads to the creation of additional administrative MD entries, increased technical MD, corresponding file pointers, and if entered correctly increased intellectual property MD. MD Input in the Archivematica Metadata Interface leads to one descriptive MD-set for the whole SIP and therefore cannot provide specific information for each data object in the information package. In comparison the CSV-file provides fields for every data-object in the data-set. In case of e.g. insufficient file-titles and author names, this would support necessary alterations in descriptive metadata to index data-objects in collections to create consistent files according to file plans, classification and uniform description rules. Additional information that cannot be covered with the DC element set, but contain vital information about provenance, file history and preservation regulations, can be entered in the CSV-file. The used terms in the CSV-file columns are used as tags for the MD elements in the METS XML file. That safeguards the documentation and expression of these information.

Combining descriptive MD input with the Archivematica UI and a CSV-file is possible, redundant information may create error messages. Currently the provided Rights Interface and the selectable options for IPR create the boundaries for entering administrative metadata. Currently it is not possible to correctly automatically extract and process PREMIS elements from a CSV-file. If the provided rights options are not suitable, the creation of an alternative is needed to satisfy the needs for IPR input.

VI Administrative Analysis: Preliminary Agreements and Administrative Preparations

6.1 Introduction

The Digital Preservation Survey 2016 by Henry revealed that the main driver for storing digital information in Welsh archives is historical preservation, legal requirements and to sustain public access. The most popular file formats are the one for text files, bitmap graphic files, spread-sheet files, and video files. Mostly descriptive metadata comes with those files, and institutions with EDRMS or similar software provide descriptive, technical, and administrative metadata. The majority store their data on external drives or remote servers.

The preliminary phase in PAIMAS features three sub-phases, with the second sub-phase preliminary definition, feasibility and assessment containing the most actions to be executed. Mostly the focus lies on identifying and defining information to be achieved, quality and quantity of digital objects, and consensus on secure and validated transfer and submission conditions. The Archivemata installation is currently in testing and intends to be the future solution for the Welsh archives. PAIMAS recommendations for the preliminary phase demands close work with the producer. In order to answer the question in Research Objective 2, the questionnaire sets out to gather information about metadata and rights management in Welsh digital preservation institutions, as well as statements to PAIMAS relevant topic such as designated communities and preservation relevant information.

6.2 Methodology

6.2.1 Qualitative Data Collection Methodology

To gather insights on current experiences with ingest and pre-ingest of digital objects in Welsh archives the questionnaire targets professional members of the ARCW. To achieve highly subjective and unique responses, a self-completed questionnaire distributed by electronic mail was chosen. According to Saunders et al. (2016, p.441) self-completed questionnaires using email contacts assure a high confidence that the right person responds, the contamination or distortion of response is low, the likely response rate varies from 30-50%. According to Bryman (2016, p.222-224) self-administrated questionnaires tends to have more closed-ended answers, an easy to follow design and are shorter than structured interviews, which can have more open-ended

questions and complex design. The advantages of self-administrated questionnaires over structured interviews are that they are cheaper and quicker to administrate, accompanied by the absence of interviewer effects, the consistency of the question order and the convenience for the participants is maintained. The disadvantages cover the inability to adjust, extend and explain the questions during the interaction with the participants.

The purposive small-scale population is homogenous and limited: eight information professionals of ARCW were invited in order to gain insight on the current situation in Welsh digital preservation institutions. Since the ARCW members are located all across Wales and the dissertation time period is limited, the researcher decided to execute a self-administrated written questionnaire to enable the participants to reply in a comfortable fashion, over a certain amount of days with the possibility to edit and refine their answers. Obtaining the replies written by the participants themselves minimises the risk of mis-translation of recorded audio interviews, and enables the immediate analysis in EXCEL without transcribing the responses.

6.2.2 Questionnaire Design

The questionnaire featured nine questions with the following characteristics:

- Q1: Personal Data. This information does not appear in the analysis; the answers are anonymized.
- Q2: Open-ended Question.
- Q3: Multiple-Choice question with open-ended alternative answer option.
- Q4: Multiple-Choice question with open-ended alternative answer option.
- Q5: Open-ended Question.
- Q6: Open-ended Question.
- Q7: Open-ended Question.
- Q8: Multiple-Choice question with open-ended alternative answer option.
- Q9: Multiple-Choice question with open-ended alternative answer option.

The complete questionnaire design, including introductory text and consensus information are displayed in *Appendix B*.

To enable convenient access and participation circumstances the questionnaire was published on [soscisurvey.de](https://www.soscisurvey.de)¹⁰, exclusive access was secured through a password. Only the chosen participants were provided with the password, the questionnaire was online available for 14 days. SoSci provides secure servers, questionnaire creation tools, and the export of data collections in CSV, SPSS, R.

6.3 Results Online Questionnaire

From the invited 8 people, 5 participated (63%). Excel was used to analyse the qualitative and quantitative answers, all graphs are displayed in this chapter, example equations are provided in the *Appendix C*. The graphs representing the multiple choice answers are pie-charts, bar-charts represent the qualitative information extracted from the open-ended questions. The numbers above each bar represents the frequency of the answer and not the population, therefore one participant can provide several answers. Following the question box the charts are displayed accompanied by the result round up.

¹⁰ Software and tools for scientific surveys. URL: <https://www.soscisurvey.de/index.php?page=home&l=eng> [Accessed 7 Sept. 2016].

2. How does your institution provide authentic and secure data transfer to the Archive without altering crucial information such as “created” or “last modified” in the data property information during the transfer process?

Figure 30: Proportional Answer Ratio Question 2 – Secure Data Transfer to Archive.

Capturing the current state of transferring data securely from the depositor to the archive reveals that the majority of the participants have no digital preservation system in place but are working towards a solution, in this case Archivemata. One institution has a policy alongside a workflow and necessary forms for data transfer from public depositor in place. There is a distinction between digitised material and born digital material: digitised material is stored in Fedora, born digital material can be managed with Archivemata. Another distinction is between data transferred from a public depositor or from a council depositor. For public transfer a digital preservation policy is in place, accompanied by workflow guidance and accession and audit trail forms. The original data stays stored on the original storage carrier, no experience with a deposit via a secure web-interface yet. Council objects may provide object history and audit trails within their EDRMS record, the transfer needs to be approved by the appropriate council officer, who signs off the final documents as well. Only preservation formats will be accepted.

3. Which of the following permissions between Producer and Archive are featured in deposit license/ agreement of your institution? This is a multiple choice answer.

- _ copyright permission
- _ migration permission (for the purpose of preservation)
- _ emulation permission (for the purpose of preservation)
- _ If not, how does your institution handle these points?

Multiple choice results in graphs:

Figure 31: Proportional Answer Ratio Q3 – Copyright Permission.

Figure 33: Proportional Answer Ratio Q3 – Migration Permission.

Figure 32: Proportional Answer Ratio Q3 – Emulation Permission.

Figure 34: Proportional Answer Ratio Q3 – Alternative Answer.

The answers in the alternative answer text field show:

Figure 35: Proportional Answer Ratio Question 3 – Permission Management.

Question 3 aimed to establish what preservation permissions are currently covered in deposit agreements and if there is a specific distinction between migration and emulation. The multiple-choice options reveal that copyright and migration permissions are dominant, emulation is not explicitly mentioned. The majority of participants provided an insight with the alternative answer option, it is apparent that the depositor controls and assigns rights, and can retain copyright. It is interesting that two participants stated that copyright and migration are mentioned in the deposit agreement, three participating institutions state the combination of migration and an alternative.

4. How does your institution capture descriptive metadata and especially preservation relevant information such as: provenance, version history, creator history for the following scenarios? And how are links between digital object and metadata provided and documented (e.g. csv, excel, or xml files)?

a) digital objects (DO) managed by an EDRMS

b) digital objects managed in local file structures without an EDRMS

Multiple choice results in graphs:

Figure 36: Proportional Answer Ratio Q4 – Digital Objects managed by EDRMS.

Figure 37: Proportional Answer Ratio Q4 – EDRMS Alternative Answer.

Figure 39: Proportional Answer Ratio Q4 – Digital Objects in Local File Structures.

Figure 38: Proportional Answer Ratio Q4 – Local File Structure Alternative Answer.

The answers in the alternative answer text field show:

a) digital objects managed by an EDRMS

Figure 40: Proportional Answer Ratio Question 4 – Digital Objects managed by EDRMS.

b) digital objects managed in local file structures without an EDRMS

Figure 41: Proportional Answer Ratio Question 4 – Digital Objects managed in Local File Structure.

This question set out to capture the management of digital objects with an EDRMS, and in local file structures without a system to document and management them. The graphs about the multiple-choice answers display that all the participants answered for both cases and provided free text answers. The EDRMS of one institution provides an automated audit trail for technical metadata, descriptive metadata can be added manually, in addition information based on classification schemes and file plans can be extracted automatically; however, the EDRMS is not compliant to any archival standard. From the bar chart, it can be seen that currently cataloguing software and especially CALM¹¹ is used to capture preservation specific information in the participating institutions. The institution with an EDRMS captures the provided metadata from the OS and software (e.g. Microsoft Office files metadata) of their unstructured files in local storages.

5. Archivematica provides a set of rights to manage in the user interface. How does your institution capture and manage the rights for “Copyright/ Statute/ License/ Donor/ Policy/ Other” currently? Perhaps in a standardized format and machine processable?

Figure 42: Proportional Answer Ratio Question 5 – Current Rights Management.

¹¹ Databases and Collection Management System. URL: <http://alm.axiell.com/calm-support-resources> [Accessed 7 Sept. 2016].

With the Archivematica intellectual property rights management interface in mind this question aimed to establish the current approach on capturing this crucial information. The analysis of the open-ended question reveals that for the time being, in the majority of institutions, the accession process documents this information. One institution uses CALM, an accession form and provides PREMIS cross-mapping. Another inserts the rights information directly into a METS file during the ingest.

6. How does your institution distinguish between intellectual property rights (IPR) management for access and preservation? If not applicable: What is your personal opinion on providing agreements for preservation IPR (for the Archive) and access IPR (for the User) separately?

Figure 43: Proportional Answer Ratio Question 6 – Intellectual Property Rights Management for Access and Preservation.

Following the previous question, question 5 focusses on different intellectual property rights for the archive and for the user instead of one universal rule. It is apparent from this bar-chart that license regulations and copyright regulations are the main driver for access and use permissions. The license and copyright agreements cover reprographics and fees, accompanied by strict use permissions. Granted licenses obey copyright law and maybe need additional clarification depending on the object and the use request.

7. How does your institution determine “designated communities” for local authority digital data? If that is not defined, what is your personal attempt of a definition?

Figure 44: Proportional Answer Ratio Question 7 – Definition Designated Communities.

A reoccurring term in the OAIS and PAIMAS terminology and concepts is designated communities. The definition of that user group contains important limits and rules for use scenarios. The identification and definition of designated communities has direct implications on the creation of SIP, its rights management and metadata. What is interesting in this data is that “anyone” appears in 25% of the answers, followed by a distinction of a mixed population of general public, special interest groups, stakeholders, individuals and organisation.

8. In your personal opinion: What use options should be available for local authority data objects in use scenarios? Up to date the regular access and authorization rules while handling data and metadata are read (view and print off), create (new objects and elements), edit (alter and edit), and delete (remove, preferably with audit trail). This is a multiple choice answer.

_ READ _ CREATE
 _ EDIT _ DELETE _ NONE of the above, because ...

Multiple choice results in graphs:

Figure 45: Proportional Answer Ratio Q8 – Allow CREATE for Data Objects.

Figure 46: Proportional Answer Ratio Q8 – Allow READ for Data Objects.

Figure 48: Proportional Answer Ratio Q8 – Allow EDIT for Data Objects.

Figure 47: Proportional Answer Ratio Q8 – Allow DELETE for Data Objects.

The answers in the alternative answer text field show:

Figure 49: Proportional Answer Ratio Question 8 – Use Options for Data Objects.

Having Haynes (2004) statement about current popular use options in mind, this questions explores the point of views regarding use options for digital objects of local authority material. To summarize the multiple-choice answers: reading, including viewing and printing should be allowed for data objects, any other option should be denied according to the participants. The majority of participants did not provide an alternative answer text, the one contributing states that the data manager should be allowed to execute all options for data objects, whereas the user should only be allowed to read (view and print off).

9. In your personal opinion: What use options should be available for local authority metadata in use scenarios? Up to date the regular access and authorization rules while handling data and metadata are read (view and print off), create (new objects and elements), edit (alter and edit), and delete (remove, preferably with audit trail). This is a multiple choice answer.

- _ READ
 - _ CREATE
- _ EDIT
 - _ DELETE
- _ NONE of the above, because ...

Multiple choice results in graphs:

Figure 51: Proportional Answer Ratio Q9 – Allow READ for Metadata.

Figure 50: Proportional Answer Ratio Q9 – Allow CREATE for Metadata.

Figure 52: Proportional Answer Ratio Q9 – Allow DELETE for Metadata.

Figure 53: Proportional Answer Ratio Q9 – Allow EDIT for Metadata.

The answers in the alternative answer text field show:

Figure 54: Proportional Answer Ratio Question 9 – Use Options for Metadata.

The last question takes the previous scenario but focusses on metadata. There is this point of view in the information professional community that metadata creators have intellectual property rights on their work (metadata records). Another idea is that perhaps there is a need in the future to alter the metadata information and therefore agreements and alteration allowance are necessary. The pie-charts show a similar result as the previous outcomes: the read option for metadata should be allowed, all other options should be denied. Consequently, the alternative answer provides the same point of view that the data manager should be allowed to execute all options for metadata, whereas the user should only be allowed to read (view and print off).

6.4 Conclusion

To summarize the results of the online questionnaire it is important to acknowledge the main themes: rights capturing and management; application of capable software. DPS or repositories to support secure storage and transfer are in planning (Figure 31-34); mainly the depositor assigns rights (Figure 35); migration as preservation strategy is popular, the alternative emulation is not specifically mentioned (Figure 35). One institution has metadata (MD) capture covered by

VII PAIMAS Evaluation of Archivemata Pre-Ingest

7.1 Introduction

According to the Producer-Archive Interface Methodology Abstract Standard (PAIMAS) the preliminary phase defines the information to be achieved and leads to a preliminary agreement between the producer and archive at the end of that phase. Since the Archivemata installation is in testing phase and ARCW works towards creating guidance on how to submit and use this preservation software, the next step after understanding how to edit metadata in and for Archivemata in this research is to work through the PAIMAS recommendations and actions for the preliminary phase. PAIMAS provides guidance on interaction and decision making for the data producer and the archive. The recommendation is aligned to four phases:

- Preliminary Phase
- Formal Definition Phase
- Transfer Phase
- Validation Phase

Each phase includes a set of sub-phases with a number of actions, the intended products of each phase is an agreement document.

In virtue of the testing status of the Archivemata installation, the researcher decided to focus on the preliminary-phase only. To follow through the complete set of phases, an actual interaction with a data-producer and working for the ingesting archive is necessary to provide information about feasibility, costs, and circumstances in the archive. Based on the action table and recommendations on defining the digital objects and conditions in PAIMAS, the transfer and ingest-function of Archivemata is investigated. The aim of this criteria based evaluation is to determine the usability of the Archivemata ingest functionality to create pre-ingest guidance, and targets Research Objective 4.

7.2 Methodology

7.2.1 Criteria based Evaluation Methodology

Chen et al. (2011, p.3) concluded that the nature of the information system and the specific objectives and goals are the main driver in evaluation of information systems, with formative and summative criteria-based evaluations as the popular approaches. Referring to (Clarke, 1999; Robson, 2002; Lagsten and Goldkuhl, 2008) evaluation research is summarized as purpose driven rather than focussed on data collection, using current insights to determine the effectiveness, quality of effects and consequences. Evaluation research aims to provide recommendations and help for decision-making. Referring to (Cronholm and Goldkuhl, 2003) the information system lifecycle provides different objectives, goals and outcomes in every stage. Chen et al. (2011) differentiate the nature of the evaluation in summative and formative, accompanied by different strategies such as goal-based, goal-free and criteria based. Summative evaluation method targets decision-makers, applies quantitative data collection and uses independent one-way communication. The experiments and quantitative measures result in limited data collections and formal reports towards the end of the evaluation process (Chen et al., 2011, p.5). Evaluation research in social sciences “denotes the study of the impact of an intervention, such as new social policy or a new innovation in organization” (Bryman, 2016, p.287). Evaluation research in business management intends to evaluate the quality and extend of a program, policy, strategy or process. Comparing the effectiveness of the investigated circumstance is a key method, resulting in a theoretical contribution to understand the existing quality and cause of that quality (Saunders et al., 2016, p.176). According to Chen et al. (2001, p.7, 10) the main features of a summative evaluation with criteria-based strategy contains cognitive walkthroughs and a heuristic evaluation. Consequently, the information system development is completed, the software environment is functioning properly and the evaluation focus is on usability and quality assurance.

Goal-based or goal-free summative or formative approaches were ineligible because these methodologies aim for evaluation during the information system development, are exploratory in terms of risks and events that can have negative impact on the system, additionally these methods use focus groups and expert interviews to determine the implementations of the information

system. Since the information system (Archivematica) is fully developed and in place, the researcher favours the criteria-based evaluation method to determine the accessibility and usability quality. In order to execute the criteria-based method the Producer Archive Interface Methodology Abstract Standard (PAIMAS) serves the purpose of a predefined set of principles. The dissertation author is aware that focussing on defined principles can lead to ignorance towards other important factors (Cronholm and Goldkuhl, 2003), however the specific focus of this dissertation lies with the ingest functionality of Archivematica and subsequent pre-ingest preparations. The Archivematica installation at the NLW is in a testing phase and functions properly, using Pydio as transfer storage, AtoM as access system was not available.

7.2.2 PAIMAS Evaluation of Archivematica Pre-Ingest

The aims of the PAIMAS preliminary phase are:

- “- to identify the primary information which the Archive must preserve;
- to establish a preliminary definition of the different Data Objects that will be transmitted to the Archive by the Producer;
- to analyze all aspects of feasibility;
- to decide on the feasibility of the Producer-Archive Project, from the Producer’s as well as from the Archive’s point of view;
- to make an estimate of the required resources;
- to draw up a Summary Document and, if appropriate, a preliminary agreement;”

(CCSDS, 2004, p.23)

The Preliminary Phase includes three subphases 1) first contact, 2) preliminary definition, feasibility and assessment, 3) establishment of a preliminary agreement.

- 1) First contact features one action with two steps.
- 2) Preliminary definition, feasibility and assessment features 12 actions with several steps each.
- 3) Establishment of a preliminary agreement features one action with two steps.

7.3 Results

Figure 57: Proportional Ratio of answerable PAIMAS actions.

Figure 56: Proportional Ratio of answerable PAIMAS actions with research insights.

The PAIMAS preliminary phase features 46 actions, of which 21 can be answered with information extracted from Henry’s survey in 2016, the Archivemata documentation, and the questionnaire. The preliminary phase applies a lot of feasibility and cost assessment, that cannot be followed through in this research scenario since there is no actual interaction with a data-producer and no actual archive. The actions that are unable to be answered with the current sources are listed in the Appendix. The following tables show the actions with Henry’s survey (Table 11) and the Archivemata documentation (Table 12).

Action Code	Henry Digital Preservation Survey 2016
P-7	Assess the planned duration of the preservation of this information by the Archive
P-9	Make a preliminary identification of the Data Object
P-19	Estimate the data volume
P-20	Assess the permanent data volume
P-21	Assess the storage capability needed for the ingest process
P-23	Identify requirements for confidentiality and authentication between Producer and Archive
P-25	Identify requirements for confidentiality and authentication between Archive and Consumer

Table 11: Overview PAIMAS actions that can be answered with Digital Preservation Survey2016 by Henry.

Henry's survey (2016) reveals that the majority of digital information needs to be stored permanently, and other than that ranges from 7 till 100 years (P-7). The most common file formats in Welsh Archives are text files and bitmap, followed by audio files, video files, and spreadsheet files (P-9). Additionally the majority of institutions need secure data storage for at least 100 GB, tending towards exceeding 1 TB (P-20, P-21). External drives and remote servers are the most common storage place in Welsh Archives at the moment. If digital information are controlled and management with a system then CALM and inhouse solutions are popular (P-23). The main driver for storing digital information is historical preservation, legal requirements and to sustain public access (P-25).

Action Code	Archivematica Documentation
P-6	Define Consumer Access to the Information
P-10 – P-13	Define the Rules, Standards and Tools
P-24	Identify requirements for security.
P-26	Identify Standards and tools
P-30	Define the conditions for access to data
P-37	Supply information on SIP Validation

Table 12: Overview PAIMAS actions that can be answered with Archivematica Documentation.

Archivematica itself does not control the access rules, however enables to add the needed information about copyright and licenses. A compatible access and discovery system is AtoM, where user classes and restrictions can be regulated (P-6). Archivematica provides a Format Policy Registry (FPR) for defining file formats, including the following features: formats, groups, rules, tools. PRONOM ID can be used as source for identifying file formats (e.g. with the FIDO tool), the described format is saved in the METS file. Archivematica distinguishes between preservation and access format. The FPR groups the file formats in the most common types from Audio, over GIS, to Word Processing. The Format Policy Rules cover Purpose, Format, Command for specific file type. The following format policy rules for file ingest include: characterization, extraction, normalization, event detail, transcription, verification. Dublin Core and PREMIS are the provided metadata standards. To manage and document the TRAC standard for auditing Trusted Digital Repositories is recommended (P-10 – P-13). Archivematica provides check-sums,

virus checking, format identification and validation, and metadata extraction. Furthermore Archivemata is able to ingest object registries from Pydio as well as compressed and zipped data packages. Data Objects that are zipped into a data archive/ package retain a specific state in this container and can not be modified (P-24). Archivemata is compliant to the ISO-OAIS functional model and uses METS, PREMIS and Dublin Core in their micro-services. PRONOM ID is the source for the file format identification tool to check the submitted files against (P-26). Archivemata demands a decision for access or preservation, and AtoM provides a range of user-access functions: researcher; contributor; editor; translator; administrator (P-30). Archivemata will run through micro-services to validate the transfer such as checksum verification, virus-scan, secure transfer report, file format validation. The crucial step is the appraisal for SIP preservation: this decision, if the automatic format identification and validation provided by Archivemata is correct, leads to either deletion or keeping of the SIP (P-37) (Artefactual Inc., 2015).

From the 21 answerable actions 6 can be answered with the insights from the transfer and ingest testing of Archivemata and the questionnaire results (Table 13).

Action Code	Questionnaire and Archivemata Test
P-3	Identify the Content Information to be preserved
P-4	Identify the complementary information: The Representation Information and Preservation Description Information (PDI).
P- 5	Identify the Designated Community
P-25	Identify requirements for confidentiality and authentication between Archive and Consumer
P-29	Assess the problem of intellectual property
P-34	Make a preliminary definition of the SIPs

Table 13: Overview PAIMAS actions that can be answered with this research.

P-3 - Identify the Content Information to be preserved

The data objects of the testing SIP include a text document, a spreadsheet document, and a PDF document. The target of this step is to define the content information of the data objects, to plan preservation activities accordingly. Identifying the content information of the testing SIP reveals the following:

Table 14: Overview content information of test data objects.

File Type	Title	Content Majority	Content Minority	Born digitally
Microsoft Word 97 – 2003 Document (.doc)	merton_summary_accounts_2009-10_final	Text	Website-Links Tables Diagram/Charts	yes
Microsoft Excel 97-2003 Worksheet (.xls)	BradfordCouncilProperty	1 Spreadsheet	Sorting Ability	yes
PDF File (.pdf)	20160106-_WPS_2016_ New_Bulletin_Format_Revised_FINAL- _O	Text	Website-Links Graphics Charts	yes

P-4 - Identify the complementary information:

The Representation Information and Preservation Description Information (PDI).

The next action demands to identify the representation information and preservation description information (PDI). Since the test digital objects were not managed with an EDRMS, they only inherit their system specific information. The following chart displays the available representation information needed to correctly render the data objects, and preservation description information such as provenance, fixity and context. The overview shows that basic general descriptive information can be extracted from the file itself, however information about authors and creators might not be complete or just in initials. Additionally the file names might not be conformant to general descriptions and perhaps need a uniform description.

Table 15: Overview representation information and preservation description information of test data objects.

Representation Information File Name(.File Type)	Descriptive Representation Information Availability	Standards for Representative Information Availability
<p>Microsoft Word 97 – 2003 Document (.doc)</p>	<p><i>File Properties:</i></p> <p><u>Origin:</u></p> <p>Authors; Last saved by; Revision Number; Program Name; Company; Content Created; Date Last Saved; Last printed; Total Editing Time;</p> <p><u>File:</u></p> <p>Name; Type; Folder Path; Date created; Date modified; Size; Attributes; Owner; Computer</p>	<p>Microsoft File Properties</p> <p>Microsoft Word Properties</p>
<p>Microsoft Excel 97-2003 Worksheet (.xls)</p>	<p><i>File Properties:</i></p> <p><u>Origin:</u></p> <p>Authors; Last saved by; Program Name; Company; Content Created; Date Last Saved; Content Type;</p> <p><u>File:</u></p> <p>Name; Type; Folder Path; Date created; Date modified; Size; Attributes; Owner; Computer</p>	<p>Microsoft File Properties</p> <p>Microsoft Excel Properties</p>
<p>20160106-_WPS_2016_ New_Bulletin_Format_Revised_FINAL- _O(.pdf)</p>	<p><i>File Properties:</i></p> <p>Name; Type; Folder Path; Size; Date created; Date modified; Attributes; Owner; Computer</p>	<p>Microsoft File Properties</p> <p>Adobe Properties</p>

P-5 - Identify the Designated Community

Identifying designated communities means to identify user groups that are interested in the collections, and therefore should be able to understand the terminology, concepts and contents of the material contained in the collections. Depending on the categorization, certain user groups need more support and context information to be able to use and comprehend certain materials. Additionally access and use rights might be granted according to the status of the designated user group a customer is assigned to. The questionnaire revealed that a designated community in terms of the local authority content is a mixed population of individuals and institutions, the overall aim is the general public (Figure 44).

P-25 - Identify requirements for confidentiality and authentication between Archive and Consumer

This action aims to determine how a secure transfer from the data producer to the archive can be assured, including safeguarding authentic information with the aid of encryption, digital signatures and check-sums. The questionnaire reveals that digital preservation and repository software such as Fedora is used to provide a secure transfer environment. Additionally one institution has a policy including workflow guidance and accession and audit trail forms in place. The majority of institutions are currently working on implementing secure transfer methods (Figure 30). The Pydio installation of the NLW provides a secure storage for transferred data objects and registries. Depositing institutions with a cataloguing system and repository might provide coherent data objects and metadata-records. Archivematica provides processes and tools to check and validate the transferred data objects, before ingesting them.

P-29 - Assess the problem of intellectual property

Determining the intellectual property rights and whether they will be transferred to the archive along with the data object is the target of this action. The recommendation suggests to set up legalization documents and define what obligation the archive has. Furthermore, PAIMAS recommends the distinction between access and preservation agreements for intellectual property

rights to secure the vital material. Concerning the rights capturing and management the questionnaire reveals that the majority of institutions capture rights in the accession process. Mostly depositors to ARCW organizations assign rights concerning copy-right, licenses, or preservation modification (emulation/ migration) (Figure 35).

P-34 - Make a preliminary definition of the SIPs

This action requires making a preliminary definition of the SIPs. The transfer and ingest functionality testing of Archivematica revealed the following varieties of submission ready data-sets:

- A) Data-set contains: single data file and CSV with descriptive MD, and additional rights MD.
- B) Data-set contains: multiple files and CSV with descriptive MD, and additional rights MD.
- C) Data-set contains: single data file and CSV with descriptive MD, additional rights MD, and Submission Documentation.
- D) Data-set contains: multiple files and CSV with descriptive MD, additional rights MD, and Submission Documentation.

The ideal SIP would feature descriptive metadata and rights information for the whole SIP entered in the Archivematica interface, an additional CSV file with specific descriptive metadata for each data object in the SIP, and finally a submission documentation to document all important agreements between depositor and archive.

7.4 Conclusion

Evaluating the usability quality of the Archivemata ingest and define components for the pre-ingest reveals that Archivemata is a suitable digital preservation system and scores positive results in terms of tools, standards, and validation. Henry's survey shows that information about preservation time and identification of data objects, data volumes, and storage and transfer circumstances can be determined. Based on this insight an actual cooperation and negotiation with a data-producer can lead to positive results because the majority of preliminary actions can be followed through. Focussing on the PAIMAS preliminary actions that can be answered with the results and insights from the purposive small-sample data collection, and the technical analysis of the transfer and ingest functionalities of Archivemata in this dissertation, 7 actions remain. Identifying the features of the requested entities shows that certain information file origin and file history can be extracted from data-objects, which are not managed by an EDRMS. That implies metadata curation to fulfil the minimum Dublin Core element set is necessary and crucial to create a consistent data-set ready for submission. The definition of designated communities in the questionnaire reveals no clear distinction, only superior categories. That implies that work on creating actual categories according to content types is needed. The need for a digital preservation system is currently answered by applying cataloguing software to capture metadata. It is interesting that cataloguing systems are used to substitute EDRMS and digital preservation systems. That implies that machine readable metadata-records are available, which would decrease the manually curation effort. Efforts are made to capture and manage intellectual property rights, showing that copyright is the superior regulation influencing preservation and access. The ideal SIP would feature metadata and rights information for the whole SIP entered in the Archivemata interface, an additional CSV file with specific metadata for each data object in the SIP, and finally a submission documentation to document all important agreements and details between depositor and archive.

VIII Discussion

Kaye (2011) stated that trustworthy and reliable documents consist inextricably of linked objects, their metadata and descriptions. The Archivemata ingest functionality test in *Chapter 5* shows that the transformation of submitted data sets into a submission information package (SIP) and later into an archival information package (AIP) meets that requirement by generating the extensible mark-up language (XML) file that includes all descriptive, administrative, technical, use, and preservation information. In addition, every data object in the submitted data set is allocated with the corresponding metadata elements and right permissions. The AIP contains the original data object, its preservation and access version, the necessary metadata information and rights licenses. According to Haynes 5- point metadata model a complete metadata-record improves the resources description; information retrieval; resource management; ownership and authenticity; and interoperability of the corresponding asset. This can be accomplished with Archivemata metadata enhancement.

Standards, models and frameworks play a big role in digital preservation, metadata management and license regulations. Haynes (2004) summarized the implementation of XML for digital preservation activities as beneficial for expressing syntactic metadata by applying mark-up and tags to enable interoperable information exchange. The technical analysis of Archivemata revealed the implementation of several standards such as the Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard (METS) to create XML files, accompanied by the Preservation Metadata Implementation Strategies (PREMIS) to structure and complete the metadata sets. At the moment Dublin Core is the default metadata standard to enter descriptive metadata, administrative metadata is covered with PREMIS.

The main result of the technical analysis of the Archivemata ingest by executing a test-series with different SIP revealed that the decision is crucial whether to use the Archivemata interface to enter metadata and rights information, or provide this information in a CSV to accompany the data objects in the SIP. This finding relates to Waugh's (2007) remark that an ingest function has to be a balanced in order to support the consistent data-set creation and submission. Based on

the list-view of the Archivemata transfer and ingest areas, the first impression of the user interface is not intuitive. The interfaces to enter metadata and rights are comprehensible, however it is important to know that adding the metadata in Archivemata has to be executed right after the transfer and before following through to the ingest micro-services, otherwise the automatically generated METS XML file will not contain the entered information. The insight, that input in the Archivemata Metadata Interface applies for the whole information package is crucial as well and impacts on the quality control of the information package that is to be created for submission. The importance of quality control in pre-ingest and ingest processes were strongly emphasised (Dürr et al., 2008; Kärberg, 2013; UK Data Archive, 2014). Several authors stated their opinion that the normalization of data and metadata should be done by the data producer in order to reduce the risks of accidental manipulation in the ingest process (Waugh, 2007; Sheldon, 2010; Oliver and Harvey, 2016). That implies the following for the institution using and providing Archivemata: in addition to spread awareness about that extraordinary requirement of this digital preservation system, the data submitter needs to be provided with forms and default CSV-files to support convenient and easy metadata input. Especially digital preservation- and special information such as retention schedules, manifestations, collection links can be entered in the CSV-files to supplement the standard descriptive information in Dublin Core (Research Objective 1). Secondly the preserving institution has to decide what information to enter manually in the Archivemata user interface, and what to ingest automatically with the aid of said CSV-files. In terms of large collections and numerous data objects in submission ready data-sets the amount of work curating and adding metadata can be reduced by only utilizing CSV-files for descriptive metadata in Dublin Core. In the current state of Archivemata (1.5) the automatically processing of administrative metadata in PREMIS is not possible yet.

The administrative analysis in *Chapter 6* aimed to capture the current situation about metadata and intellectual property rights management in digital preservation institution in Wales. The basis for this data collection is the prior survey done by Henry. In order to determine what needs to be provided by the data submitter and the archive (Research Objective 2), it is necessary to capture what is currently provided. The analysis of the mostly qualitative data collection reveals that the current need for a digital preservation system is approached by using cataloguing software.

Preservation permission is dominant in deposit agreements, and the majority of institution take in the depositor permission, rather than providing a set of rights, of which the depositor can select. Predominantly the accession process and its activities capture and manage intellectual right properties, which are mostly license and copyright regulation. That implies that the access and use of data objects needs to be supported by request forms and contracts to assure compliance. Since AtoM is the corresponding access and discovery system for Archivematica, it is necessary to compare the pre-set access rights of AtoM with the license and copyrights demands of the depositor. To conclude the demands for data submitter and archive the following can be claimed:

- 1) The data submitter needs to identify and define the difference between access and preservation permission for the intellectual property rights, in order to safeguard the digital long-term preservation and archiving of the digital data objects. That includes permissions for a variety of preservation actions to cover future migration and emulation, transcending currently known file formats.
- 2) The data submitter needs to transfer the rights to edit, alter and manipulate the metadata records to the archive to ensure the quality control and completeness of the data-sets. That allows the archive to update the descriptive metadata, and improve the indexing of the whole collection.
- 3) The archive needs to provide default forms and digital templates to support convenient metadata entry, that is compliant to the intended standard of the archive.

A *good SIP* (Research Objective 3) contains the digital data-objects in their original state, a CSV-file with specific digital preservation information and additional information for each data-object. Descriptive and administrative MD that are supposed to be valid for the whole SIP are entered in the Archivematica UI. The submission documentation file includes submission agreements and other negotiation results between data submitter and archive. The usability of the Archivematica ingest is good and provided tools and standards to create trustworthy and authentic SIP, AIP and DIP (Research Objective 4). Archivematica's ability to be adjusted and extended by other software for transfer and pre-ingest storage, and access is beneficial for the adaption to current needs and circumstances.

IX Conclusion

9.1 General Conclusion

The aim of this dissertation was to comprehend and evaluate the operating principles of the transfer and ingest functionalities of Archivemata in order provide an example SIP with data objects, metadata and rights information. The research objectives included identifying provided and needed metadata; assessing the needed complementary information provided by the producer and the archive; determine components of a ready for submission and data-set and subsequently SIP; evaluation the usability of the Archivemata ingest functionality in relation to providing pre-ingest support. The literature review shows that RMS, CMS, and EDRMS provide lossless and authentic data, the questionnaire results show a lack of those systems and alternatively cataloguing software being used to bridge the gap. A novel idea is the implementation of a stage in the ingest process where the archive actively decides to accept or deny the submitted information package, Archivemata provides this option. The technical analysis of the transfer and ingest functionalities of Archivemata reveals that descriptive metadata can be automatically extracted from CSV-files with Dublin Core compliant metadata for each data object in the SIP, administrative metadata concerning intellectual rights management only can be entered in the Archivemata interface for rights management. That implies that a complete SIP needs to provide a CSV-file with descriptive metadata, and manual input of administrative metadata in Archivemata is unavoidable in the current Archivemata 1.5 version. The qualitative data analysis showed that digital preservation institution in Wales are working towards using Archivemata as digital preservation system solution, capture and manage descriptive metadata with cataloguing software, and follow the copyright and license restrictions of the depositors. The criteria based evaluation of the ingest functionality of Archivemata confirmed the good quality of the technical architecture of this digital preservation system. Based on the insights from Henry's survey, and the questionnaire executed in this dissertation research it is apparent that an actual negotiation and cooperation between Welsh data producer and archives can be successfully followed through, since the necessary information are available and known.

9.2 Critical Reflection

The applied research methods consisted of:

- A comprehensive literature review focussing on metadata management and experiences with pre-ingest and ingest in the digital preservation community.
- A technical analysis of the transfer and ingest functionality of Archivematica by executing a series of tests with SIP contents.
- An administrative analysis of current circumstances and approaches on data, metadata and rights management in digital preservation institutions of Wales.
- A criteria based evaluation of the Archivematica pre-ingest and ingest according to PAIMAS preliminary phase actions.

Reflecting on the research methods chosen, it would have been beneficial to execute expert interviews to discuss PAIMAS specific information and provide further information on questions used. Interviewing an expert comes closer to the desired interaction with a data-producer that is necessary to follow through the PAIMAS actions. The disadvantages of the self-administrated questionnaire cover the inability to adjust, extend and explain the questions during the interaction with the participants. Additionally, participants were asked to fill in the data manually, therefore did not elicit as much information that could have been obtained via other methods. The access and discovery system AtoM was unavailable in the NLW installation, which led to no testing and no insight on how the alteration in the metadata and rights information in the test-series affects the overview and display in the access environment. The PAIMAS recommendation appeared to be complex and demanded a lot of cost assessment, which could not be followed through. A research focussing only on PAIMAS in relation with Archivematica is necessary to provide valid and deeper insight. A cooperation with an archive that wants to apply PAIMAS and has data-producers available for negotiations would have led to better and more valid results. The findings represent the current situation in Wales, but cannot be generalised, since the sample population did not capture all Welsh archives.

9.3 Recommendations

The researcher recommends following through the whole action catalogue of PAIMAS in relation to Archivematica to produce preliminary and submission agreements. These agreements support guidance and boundaries for the creation and submission of data-sets.

Further developments in supporting the automatic extraction of descriptive and administrative metadata from supplementary CSV-files in the SIP are desirable, to efficiently and effectively handle large collections and automatic bulk ingests. Future implications can be decreased curation efforts based on automatized processes, and increased consistency of SIP, since human errors in curating and editing metadata in Archivematica can be minimized.

Clear permissions for the archive to alter and manipulate metadata are necessary in order to enable consistent indexing of collections, and to enter preservation relevant information that are not covered by the Dublin Core element set.

Creating a submission agreement including the following decisions is recommended:

- Does the archive only accept data-objects in preservation file-formats? OR
- Does the depositor provides the original data-objects and the Archive responsible for normalizing and migrating them with the aid of Archivematica?
- Are descriptive administrative metadata captured manually in CSV-files or provided by exported metadata-records from the EDRMS or cataloguing software?
- What is content of the Submission Documentation?
- The metadata curation permission needs to be granted for the archive to support the upgrade and fully complete the needed descriptive and administrative metadata, according to the archival standard.

9.4 Further Studies

There is a need for further studies for several elements regarding the Archivemata ingest functionalities:

- What specific additional information are needed concerning the contents and files of Local Authorities? What elements need to be added in the CSV-file to supplement the standard Dublin Core element set in order to provide improved preservation focused information?
- Does the Rights Interface provide enough options for intellectual property rights to cover the needs for Local Authority regulations or is there a need to create specific rights schemata?
- Is there a method circumvent the manual input of descriptive and administrative metadata using Archivemata, so that this information can be extracted and processed automatized?
- What tools, software, and information architecture needs to be attached to Archivemata to adjust to the needs for managing, curating, and preserving the data-sets with and without metadata records from Local Authorities?
- What is the result on following through the complete recommendations and actions of PAIMAS in relation to Archivemata?
- Are there novel use scenarios for Local Authority content in the future, that are not popular or applicable now? Will text-mining be a possible application in the future and need use-permissions adapt to that?
- What are the implications for metadata records and rights management for digitized content, that might have physical and digital manifestations?

9.5 Final Conclusion

Archivematica provides services and tools to authentically follow through the transformation of ingested data-sets into SIP, AIP and later DIP. The provided interfaces for each phase are usable, however, need some time and comprehension before efficient and effective work is possible. Entered metadata and rights information prior to the ingest phase result in a consistent and complete METS XML file for each SIP, containing all entered descriptive and administrative metadata, and automatically extracted technical metadata. The access management according to user groups is managed by the corresponding access and discovery system AtoM. Following through the complete PAIMAS recommendation in relation to the Archivematica implementation in Welsh digital preservation institutions is recommended. Archivematica provides a good basis and allows the connection with other software environments, tools and architectures to adapt to the specific need of the archive. Using CSV-files with additional information for large collections, multiple-file documents, and special attributes of data-objects offers the appropriate supplementation for the standard metadata sets provided by the Archivematica metadata and rights interfaces. All Research Objectives were achieved. Although Research Objective 2 needs more information, which could be provided by interacting with actual collections and investigation the properties and features of file-formats and contents of Local Authority Data. The recommended content of a good SIP based on the test-series is a good indication for expectable situation of small data-sets with single files. The necessary feasibility studies for ingesting data-sets into Archivematica according to PAIMAS were not followed through here, because of the research setting only using insights from data collections and the technical analysis. Institutions that plan to install Archivematica will benefit from following through the cost and feasibility studies in order to get an overview on secure transfer mechanisms and storage costs.

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Word count

18290

Appendices

Appendix A: Documentation Screenshots Archivematica Transfer and Ingest Tests

Name	Date modified	Type	Size
20160106-_WPS_2016_New_Bulletin_Format_Revised_FINAL-_O	20/06/2016 15:50	PDF File	216 KB
BradfordCouncilProperty	20/06/2016 15:50	Microsoft Excel 97...	871 KB
merton_summary_accounts_2009-10_final	20/06/2016 15:50	Microsoft Word 9...	218 KB

1) jkb-MD-Test2-noCSV-noMD_160701

Descriptive Metadata			
Descriptive Metadata Section	<dmdSec>	no	
External Descriptive Metadata	<mdRef>	no	
Internal Descriptive Metadata	<mdWrap>	100x	
Administrative Metadata			
Administrative Metadata Section	<amdSec>	62x	
Technical Metadata	<techMD>	15x	
IPR Metadata	<rightsMD>	no	
Source Metadata	<sourceMD>	no	
Digital Provenance Metadata	<digiprovMD>	100x	
File Section			
File Section	<fileSec>	20x	
File Group	<fileGrp>	24x	
Structural Map			
Structural Map	<structMap>	24x	
METS pointer	<mptr>	no	
File pointer	<fptr>	8x	
Structural Links			
Structural Links	<smLink>	no	
Behaviour Section			
Behavior	<behavior>	no	

Metadata

jkb-MD-Test2-noCSV-yesMD_160701

Title

Part of AIC

Optional: leave blank if unsure

Creator

Subject

Description

Publisher

Contributor

Date

Use ISO 8061 (YYYY-MM-DD or YYYY-MM-DD/YYYY-MM-DD)

Format

Identifier

Source

Description

Pdf shows abc

Publisher

Department ABC, Information Officer B

Contributor

Department ABC, Administrative Officer M

Date

Use ISO 8061 (YYYY-MM-DD or YYYY-MM-DD/YYYY-MM-DD)

Format

Identifier

Source

Relation

Language

|

Use ISO 639

Coverage

Rights

Copyright held by Ministry of XYZ

Create

Cancel

```

<?xml version="1.0" encoding="ASCII"?>
- <mets:mets xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.loc.gov/METS/
http://www.loc.gov/standards/mets/version18/mets.xsd" xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink"
xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xmlns:mets="http://www.loc.gov/METS/">
  <mets:metsHdr CREATEDATE="2016-07-01T09:42:54"/>
  - <mets:dmdSec ID="dmdSec_1">
    - <mets:mdWrap MDTYPE="DC">
      - <mets:xmlData>
        - <dcterms:dublincore xsi:schemaLocation="http://purl.org/dc/terms/
http://dublincore.org/schemas/xmls/qdc/2008/02/11/dcterms.xsd"
xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/" xmlns:dcterms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/">
          <dc:title>MM01</dc:title>
          <dc:creator>Ministry of XYZ</dc:creator>
          <dc:subject>Register</dc:subject>
          <dc:description>Pdf shows abc</dc:description>
          <dc:publisher>Department ABC, Information Officer B</dc:publisher>
          <dc:contributor>Department ABC, Administrative Officer M</dc:contributor>
          <dc:rights>Copyright held by Ministry of XYZ</dc:rights>
        </dcterms:dublincore>
      </mets:xmlData>
    </mets:mdWrap>
  </mets:dmdSec>

```

```

- <mets:fileSec>
  - <mets:fileGrp USE="original">
    - <mets:file ID="file-409ef89f-a13b-43d5-ac34-41f905a9bdd1" ADMID="amdSec_2" GROUPID="Group-409ef89f-a13b-43d5-ac34-41f905a9bdd1">
      <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/20160106-WPS_2016_New_Bulletin_Format_Revised_FINAL_0.pdf"/>
    </mets:file>
    - <mets:file ID="file-2074ffe5-36e2-4b98-83ca-df3e419576b8" ADMID="amdSec_3" GROUPID="Group-2074ffe5-36e2-4b98-83ca-df3e419576b8">
      <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/BradfordCouncilProperty.xls"/>
    </mets:file>
    - <mets:file ID="file-cfb7a7c2-9fda-4bcc-b2c6-1882cf20e428" ADMID="amdSec_4" GROUPID="Group-cfb7a7c2-9fda-4bcc-b2c6-1882cf20e428">
      <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/merton_summary_accounts_2009-10_final.doc"/>
    </mets:file>
  </mets:fileGrp>
  - <mets:fileGrp USE="submissionDocumentation">
    - <mets:file ID="file-82111752-749a-4e51-ae7c-71d5d1098748" ADMID="amdSec_7" GROUPID="Group-82111752-749a-4e51-ae7c-71d5d1098748">
      <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/submissionDocumentation/transfer-jkb-MD-Test2-noCSV-yesMD_160701-12444461-a957-49e6-8758-f5023e1b2c03/METS.xml"/>
    </mets:file>
  </mets:fileGrp>
  - <mets:fileGrp USE="preservation">
    - <mets:file ID="file-8bdf84a5-6f75-412c-8fda-f4e43fb792a1" ADMID="amdSec_1" GROUPID="Group-409ef89f-a13b-43d5-ac34-41f905a9bdd1">
      <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/20160106-WPS_2016_New_Bulletin_Format_Revised_FINAL_0-a205376a-c9a7-4896-96d0-f4d8b2a6749f.pdf"/>
    </mets:file>
  </mets:fileGrp>
  - <mets:fileGrp USE="metadata">
    - <mets:file ID="file-693cac37-a0a5-4239-86e6-e547100a527d" ADMID="amdSec_5" GROUPID="Group-693cac37-a0a5-4239-86e6-e547100a527d">
      <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/metadata/dc.json"/>
    </mets:file>
    - <mets:file ID="file-b5aa192d-dc83-469b-a708-d5d3e97a3f39" ADMID="amdSec_6" GROUPID="Group-b5aa192d-dc83-469b-a708-d5d3e97a3f39">
      <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/metadata/transfers/jkb-MD-Test2-noCSV-yesMD_160701-12444461-a957-49e6-8758-f5023e1b2c03/dc.json"/>
    </mets:file>
  </mets:fileGrp>
</mets:fileSec>

```

2) jkb-MD-Test2-noCSV-yesMD_160701

Descriptive Metadata			
Descriptive Metadata Section	<u><dmdSec></u>	4	DC title, creator, subject, description, publisher, contributor, rights
External Descriptive Metadata	<u>(mdRef)</u>	no	
Internal Descriptive Metadata	<u>(mdWrap)</u>	100x	
Administrative Metadata			
Administrative Metadata Section	<u><amdSec></u>	70x	
Technical Metadata	<u><techMD></u>	21x	
IPR Metadata	<u><rightsMD></u>	no	
Source Metadata	<u><sourceMD></u>	no	
Digital Provenance Metadata	<u><digiprovMD></u>	100x	
File Section			
File Section	<u><fileSec></u>	20x	
File Group	<u><fileGrp></u>	26x	
Structural Map			
Structural Map	<u><structMap></u>	24x	
METS pointer	<u><mptr></u>	no	
File pointer	<u><fptr></u>	10x	
Structural Links			
Structural Links	<u><smLink></u>	no	
Behaviour Section			
<u>Behavior</u>	<u><behavior></u>	no	

Name	Date modified	Type	Size
metadata	01/07/2016 10:47	File folder	
20160106-_WPS_2016_New_Bulletin_For...	20/06/2016 15:50	PDF File	216 KB
BradfordCouncilProperty	20/06/2016 15:50	Microsoft Excel 97...	871 KB
merton_summary_accounts_2009-10_final	20/06/2016 15:50	Microsoft Word 9...	218 KB

filename	dc.title	dcterms.issued	dc.publisher	dc.contributor
objects/20160106-	MM01	01/01/2015	Department ABC, Information Officer B	Department ABC, Administrative Officer M
objects/BradfordC	MM02	02/01/2015	Department ABC, Information Officer B	Department ABC, Administrative Officer M
objects/merton_s	MM03	03/01/2015	Department ABC, Information Officer B	Department ABC, Administrative Officer M

dc.subject	dc.subject	dc.date	dc.description	notes	dcterms.isPartOf	repository
Register	PDF	29/06/2016	Pdf shows abc	this is a test	Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q1	NLW Archivemata
Register	EXCEL	30/06/2016	EXCEL shows def	this is a test	Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q2	NLW Archivemata
Register	WORD	01/07/2016	WORD shows ghi	this is a test	Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q3	NLW Archivemata

dc.rights	project_website	dc.format
Copyright held by Ministry of XYZ	website address	pdf/pdf
Copyright held by Ministry of XYZ	website address	vnd.ms-excel/xls
Copyright held by Ministry of XYZ	website address	msword/doc

```

<?xml version="1.0" encoding="ASCII"?>
- < mets: mets xsi: schemaLocation="http://www.loc.gov/METS/
http://www.loc.gov/standards/mets/version18/mets.xsd" xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink"
xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xmlns:mets="http://www.loc.gov/METS/">
  < mets: metsHdr CREATEDATE="2016-07-01T09:53:25"/>
  - < mets: dmdSec ID="dmdSec_1">
    - < mets: mdWrap MDTYPE="DC">
      - < mets: xmlData>
        - < dcterms: dublincore xsi: schemaLocation="http://purl.org/dc/terms/
http://dublincore.org/schemas/xmls/qdc/2008/02/11/dcterms.xsd"
xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/" xmlns:dcterms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/">
          < dc: title>MM01</dc: title>
          < dcterms: issued>01/01/2015</dcterms: issued>
          < dc: publisher>Department ABC, Information Officer B</dc: publisher>
          < dc: contributor>Department ABC, Administrative Officer M</dc: contributor>
          < dc: subject>Register</dc: subject>
          < dc: subject>PDF</dc: subject>
          < dc: date>29/06/2016</dc: date>
          < dc: description>Pdf shows abc</dc: description>
          < dcterms: isPartOf>Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q1</dcterms: isPartOf>
          < dc: rights>Copyright held by Ministry of XYZ</dc: rights>
          < dc: format>pdf/pdf</dc: format>
        </dcterms: dublincore>
      </mets: xmlData>
    </mets: mdWrap>
  </mets: dmdSec>
  - < mets: dmdSec ID="dmdSec_2">
    - < mets: mdWrap MDTYPE="OTHER" OTHERMDTYPE="CUSTOM">
      - < mets: xmlData>
        < notes>this is a test</notes>
        < repository>NLW Archivematica</repository>
        < project_website>website address</project_website>
      </mets: xmlData>
    </mets: mdWrap>
  </mets: dmdSec>

```

```

- < mets: fileSec>
  - < mets: fileGrp USE="original">
    - < mets: file ID="file-5f3f54c3-dca2-417e-bbe2-b4adf1242771" ADMID="amdSec_2" GROUPID="Group-5f3f54c3-dca2-417e-bbe2-b4adf1242771">
      < mets: Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/20160106_WPS_2016_New_Bulletin_Format_Revised_FINAL_0.pdf"/>
    </mets: file>
    - < mets: file ID="file-7fd1a2b4-1cd7-440b-bb52-a1b410d69d99" ADMID="amdSec_3" GROUPID="Group-7fd1a2b4-1cd7-440b-bb52-a1b410d69d99">
      < mets: Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/BradfordCouncilProperty.xls"/>
    </mets: file>
    - < mets: file ID="file-bd9af17e-1611-42ab-bc0d-4d6488428a8b" ADMID="amdSec_4" GROUPID="Group-bd9af17e-1611-42ab-bc0d-4d6488428a8b">
      < mets: Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/merton_summary_accounts_2009-10_final.doc"/>
    </mets: file>
  </mets: fileGrp>
  - < mets: fileGrp USE="submissionDocumentation">
    - < mets: file ID="file-72811a15-a019-4731-8fc9-35254bb90c98" ADMID="amdSec_6" GROUPID="Group-72811a15-a019-4731-8fc9-35254bb90c98">
      < mets: Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/submissionDocumentation/transfer-jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-noMD_160701-9620f424-65bb-49c8-ac8d-588615bc4d60/METS.xml"/>
    </mets: file>
  </mets: fileGrp>
  - < mets: fileGrp USE="preservation">
    - < mets: file ID="file-22621ec9-2c35-46c8-82ef-dc35f00ee38c" ADMID="amdSec_1" GROUPID="Group-5f3f54c3-dca2-417e-bbe2-b4adf1242771">
      < mets: Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/20160106_WPS_2016_New_Bulletin_Format_Revised_FINAL_0-26debed5-be9f-4dce-b514-fa38daeb3b30.pdf"/>
    </mets: file>
  </mets: fileGrp>
  - < mets: fileGrp USE="metadata">
    - < mets: file ID="file-463f176c-fb7c-4485-a679-fce7a4d04d6" ADMID="amdSec_5" GROUPID="Group-463f176c-fb7c-4485-a679-fce7a4d04d6">
      < mets: Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/metadata/transfers/jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-noMD_160701-9620f424-65bb-49c8-ac8d-588615bc4d60/metadata.csv"/>
    </mets: file>
  </mets: fileGrp>
</mets: fileSec>

```

3) jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-noMD_160701

Descriptive Metadata			
Descriptive Metadata Section	< <u>dmdSec</u> >	24x	
External Descriptive Metadata	< <u>mdRef</u> >	no	
Internal Descriptive Metadata	< <u>mdWrap</u> >	100x	
Administrative Metadata			
Administrative Metadata Section	< <u>amdSec</u> >	66x	
Technical Metadata	< <u>techMD</u> >	18x	
IPR Metadata	< <u>rightsMD</u> >	no	
Source Metadata	< <u>sourceMD</u> >	no	
Digital Provenance Metadata	< <u>digiprovMD</u> >	100x	
File Section			
File Section	< <u>fileSec</u> >	20x	
File Group	< <u>fileGrp</u> >	26x	
Structural Map			
Structural Map	< <u>structMap</u> >	24x	
METS pointer	< <u>mptr</u> >	no	
File pointer	< <u>fptr</u> >	9x	
Structural Links			
Structural Links	< <u>smlink</u> >	no	
Behaviour Section			
<u>Behavior</u>	< <u>behavior</u> >	no	

[Transfer](#) / [jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-yesMD_160701](#) / [Metadata](#) / [Edit](#)

Metadata

jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-yesMD_160701

Title

MMX

Part of AIC

Optional: leave blank if unsure

Creator

Ministry of XYZ

Subject

MMX Test

Description

This is description text in the Archivematica UI

Publisher

Ministry of XYZ, Department ABC

Contributor

Information Officer B

Date

Use ISO 8061 (YYYY-MM-DD or YYYY-MM-DD/YYYY-MM-DD)

Format

Identifier

0001

Source

Description

This is description text in the Archivematica UI

Publisher

Ministry of XYZ, Department ABC

Contributor

Information Officer B

An entity respon
contributions to
(ISO15836)

Date

Use ISO 8061 (YYYY-MM-DD or YYYY-MM-DD/YYYY-MM-DD)

Format

Identifier

0001

Source

Source

Relation

Relation

Language

Language

Use ISO 639

Coverage

Coverage

Rights

This is free text in the rights field.

Save Cancel

filename	dc.title	dcterms.issued	dc.subject	dc.subject	dcterms.isPartOf	dc.format	premis.copyrightStatus
objects/20160106-	MM01	01/01/2015	Register	PDF	Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q1	pdf/pdf	Deposit to Archive
objects/BradfordC	MM02	02/01/2015	Register	EXCEL	Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q2	vnd.ms-excel/xls	Deposit to Archive
objects/merton_sl	MM03	03/01/2015	Register	WORD	Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q3	msword/doc	Deposit to Archive

```

<?xml version="1.0" encoding="ASCII"?>
- <mets:mets xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.loc.gov/METS/
http://www.loc.gov/standards/mets/version18/mets.xsd" xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink"
xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xmlns:mets="http://www.loc.gov/METS/">
  <mets:metsHdr CREATEDATE="2016-07-01T13:47:34"/>
  - <mets:dmdSec ID="dmdSec_7">
    - <mets:mdWrap MDTYPE="DC">
      - <mets:xmlData>
        - <dcterms:dublincore xsi:schemaLocation="http://purl.org/dc/terms/
http://dublincore.org/schemas/xmls/qdc/2008/02/11/dcterms.xsd"
xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/" xmlns:dcterms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/">
          <dc:title>MMX</dc:title>
          <dc:creator>Ministry of XYZ</dc:creator>
          <dc:subject>MMX Test</dc:subject>
          <dc:description>This is description text in the Archivemata UI</dc:description>
          <dc:publisher>Ministry of XYZ, Department ABC</dc:publisher>
          <dc:contributor>Information Officer B</dc:contributor>
          <dc:identifier>0001</dc:identifier>
          <dc:source>Source</dc:source>
          <dc:relation>Relation</dc:relation>
          <dc:language>Language</dc:language>
          <dc:coverage>Coverage</dc:coverage>
          <dc:rights>This is free text in the rights field.</dc:rights>
        </dcterms:dublincore>
      </mets:xmlData>
    </mets:mdWrap>
  </mets:dmdSec>

```

```

- <mets:dmdSec ID="dmdSec_1">
  - <mets:mdWrap MDTYPE="DC">
    - <mets:xmlData>
      - <dcterms:dublincore xsi:schemaLocation="http://purl.org/dc/terms/
http://dublincore.org/schemas/xmls/qdc/2008/02/11/dcterms.xsd"
xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/" xmlns:dcterms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/">
        <dc:title>MM01</dc:title>
        <dcterms:issued>01/01/2015</dcterms:issued>
        <dc:subject>Register</dc:subject>
        <dc:subject>PDF</dc:subject>
        <dcterms:isPartOf>Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q1</dcterms:isPartOf>
        <dc:format>pdf/pdf</dc:format>
      </dcterms:dublincore>
    </mets:xmlData>
  </mets:mdWrap>
</mets:dmdSec>
- <mets:dmdSec ID="dmdSec_2">
  - <mets:mdWrap MDTYPE="OTHER" OTHERMDTYPE="CUSTOM">
    - <mets:xmlData>
      <premis_copyrightstatus>Deposit to Archive</premis_copyrightstatus>
    </mets:xmlData>
  </mets:mdWrap>
</mets:dmdSec>

```

```

- <mets:rightsMD ID="rightsMD_1">
  - <mets:mdWrap MDTYPE="PREMIS:RIGHTS">
    - <mets:xmlData>
      - <premis:rightsStatement xsi:schemaLocation="info:lc/xmlns/premis-v2
        http://www.loc.gov/standards/premis/v2/premis-v2-2.xsd"
        xmlns:premis="info:lc/xmlns/premis-v2">
        - <premis:rightsStatementIdentifier>
          <premis:rightsStatementIdentifierType>UUID</premis:rightsStatementIdentifierType>
          <premis:rightsStatementIdentifierValue>b728c237-2853-4caf-8331-
            8340741c22ed</premis:rightsStatementIdentifierValue>
          </premis:rightsStatementIdentifier>
          <premis:rightsBasis>Other</premis:rightsBasis>
          <premis:otherRightsInformation/>
        - <premis:linkingObjectIdentifier>
          <premis:linkingObjectIdentifierType>UUID</premis:linkingObjectIdentifierType>
          <premis:linkingObjectIdentifierValue>9b5d51f2-adc0-4f67-a129-
            9ba70ec11284</premis:linkingObjectIdentifierValue>
          </premis:linkingObjectIdentifier>
        </premis:rightsStatement>
      </mets:xmlData>
    </mets:mdWrap>
  </mets:rightsMD>

```

archivematica Transfer Ingest Archival storage Preservation planning Access Administration shiggins

Task UUID: 69b1e11-8830-44c8-8595-371501d54fc8 Start time: 2016-07-01T13:48:25
 File UUID: End time: 2016-07-01T13:48:25
 File name: jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-yesMD_160701-57c7de9e-bbd5-4561-b049-2ed2b5a3data Created time: 2016-07-01T13:48:25
 Client: archer_4 Duration: < 1 second(s)
 (exit code: 1)

Show arguments

```

restructureDIPForContentDMUpload_v0.0 --uuid="57c7de9e-bbd5-4561-b049-2ed2b5a3data" --dir "%sharedPath%watchedDirectories/uploadDIP/jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-yesMD_160701-57c7de9e-bbd5-4561-b049-2ed2b5a3data"

```

STDOUT

```

DIP UUID: 57c7de9e-bbd5-4561-b049-2ed2b5a3data
Package type: compound-file
Path to the output subfile /var/archivematica/sharedDirectory/watchedDirectories/uploadDIP/jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-yesMD_160701-57c7de9e-bbd5-4561-b049-2ed2b5a3data/objects/compound.txt
Table header: ['title', 'creator', 'subject', 'description', 'publisher', 'contributor', 'identifier', 'source', 'relation', 'language', 'coverage', 'rights', 'AIP UUID', 'file UUID', 'Filename']
Values: ['MXX', 'Ministry of XYZ', 'MXX Test', 'This is description text in the Archivematica UI', 'Ministry of XYZ, Department ABC', 'Information Officer B', '0001: 57c7de9e-bbd5-4561-b049-2ed2b5a3data', 'Source', 'Relation', 'Language', 'Coverage', 'This is free text in the rights field.', '57c7de9e-bbd5-4561-b049-2ed2b5a3data', '', 'objects']

```

STDERR

```

ERROR headers differ: /var/archivematica/sharedDirectory/watchedDirectories/uploadDIP/jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-yesMD_160701-57c7de9e-bbd5-4561-b049-2ed2b5a3data/objects/compound.txt almost certainly invalid
Reference header: ['title', 'creator', 'subject', 'description', 'publisher', 'contributor', 'identifier', 'source', 'relation', 'language', 'coverage', 'rights', 'AIP UUID', 'file UUID', 'Filename']
Differing header: ['premis_copyrightstatus', 'AIP UUID', 'file UUID', 'Filename']

```

```
- <mets:fileSec>
- <mets:fileGrp USE="original">
- <mets:file ID="file-9b5d51f2-adc0-4f67-a129-9ba70ec11284" ADMID="amdSec_2" GROUPID="Group-9b5d51f2-adc0-4f67-a129-9ba70ec11284">
  <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/20160106_WPS_2016_New_Bulletin_Format_Revised_FINAL_0.pdf"/>
</mets:file>
- <mets:file ID="file-3c6dd360-17f4-4f5a-93e0-2313c3c839c5" ADMID="amdSec_3" GROUPID="Group-3c6dd360-17f4-4f5a-93e0-2313c3c839c5">
  <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/BradfordCouncilProperty.xls"/>
</mets:file>
- <mets:file ID="file-6a38e5f9-bdfb-4c43-a7b7-fea827681218" ADMID="amdSec_4" GROUPID="Group-6a38e5f9-bdfb-4c43-a7b7-fea827681218">
  <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/merton_summary_accounts_2009-10_final.doc"/>
</mets:file>
</mets:fileGrp>
- <mets:fileGrp USE="submissionDocumentation">
- <mets:file ID="file-cf2dfa74-48f3-4a8d-a9aa-4ddb741569c6" ADMID="amdSec_8" GROUPID="Group-cf2dfa74-48f3-4a8d-a9aa-4ddb741569c6">
  <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/submissionDocumentation/transfer-jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-yesMD_160701-8ee85ad2-72f8-463c-bb8e-108982be71ca/METS.xml"/>
</mets:file>
</mets:fileGrp>
- <mets:fileGrp USE="preservation">
- <mets:file ID="file-fb6d2373-a1fd-4b94-9b28-750cc4b5fd45" ADMID="amdSec_1" GROUPID="Group-9b5d51f2-adc0-4f67-a129-9ba70ec11284">
  <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/20160106_WPS_2016_New_Bulletin_Format_Revised_FINAL_0-7936d3e3-3c29-4a43-b1ec-d81880d428be.pdf"/>
</mets:file>
</mets:fileGrp>
- <mets:fileGrp USE="metadata">
- <mets:file ID="file-34fd7122-9e61-4e24-9ee2-926e91173a01" ADMID="amdSec_5" GROUPID="Group-34fd7122-9e61-4e24-9ee2-926e91173a01">
  <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/metadata/dc.json"/>
</mets:file>
- <mets:file ID="file-b9f24688-2a10-4f91-9a1f-90d3883c6772" ADMID="amdSec_6" GROUPID="Group-b9f24688-2a10-4f91-9a1f-90d3883c6772">
  <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/metadata/transfers/jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-yesMD_160701-8ee85ad2-72f8-463c-bb8e-108982be71ca/dc.json"/>
</mets:file>
- <mets:file ID="file-874d05db-1f7c-4e82-908a-85465b0a0374" ADMID="amdSec_7" GROUPID="Group-874d05db-1f7c-4e82-908a-85465b0a0374">
  <mets:Flocat OTHERLOCTYPE="SYSTEM" LOCTYPE="OTHER" xlink:href="objects/metadata/transfers/jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-yesMD_160701-8ee85ad2-72f8-463c-bb8e-108982be71ca/metadata.csv"/>
</mets:file>
</mets:fileGrp>
</mets:fileSec>
```

4) jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-yesMD_160701

Descriptive Metadata			
Descriptive Metadata Section	< <u>dmdSec</u> >	28x	
External Descriptive Metadata	< <u>mdRef</u> >	no	
Internal Descriptive Metadata	< <u>mdWrap</u> >	+100x	
Administrative Metadata			
Administrative Metadata Section	< <u>amdSec</u> >	74x	
Technical Metadata	< <u>techMD</u> >	24x	
IPR Metadata	< <u>rightsMD</u> >	9	
Source Metadata	< <u>sourceMD</u> >	no	
Digital Provenance Metadata	< <u>digiprovmD</u> >	+100x	
File Section			
File Section	< <u>fileSec</u> >	20x	
File Group	< <u>fileGrp</u> >	26x	
Structural Map			
Structural Map	< <u>structMap</u> >	24x	
METS pointer	< <u>mptr</u> >	no	
File pointer	< <u>fptr</u> >	11x	
Structural Links			
Structural Links	< <u>smLink</u> >	no	
Behaviour Section			
<u>Behavior</u>	< <u>behavior</u> >	no	

Rights

jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-yesRightsMD_160701

Basis

Copyright

Copyright status

Copyright Status Test

Copyright jurisdiction

Copyright jurisdiction Test

Copyright determination date

2016-07-01

Use ISO 8061 (YYYY-MM-DD)

Copyright start date

2016-07-01

Use ISO 8061 (YYYY-MM-DD)

Copyright end date

Use ISO 8061 (YYYY-MM-DD)

Open End Date

Copyright documentation identifier:

Type	Type1
Value	Value1
Role	Role1

Copyright note

Copyright note test

Save

Next

Cancel

Rights

jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-yesRightsMD_160701

Basis

Statute jurisdiction

Statute citation

Statute determination date

Use ISO 8061 (YYYY-MM-DD)

Statute start date

Use ISO 8061 (YYYY-MM-DD)

Statute end date

Use ISO 8061 (YYYY-MM-DD)

Open End Date

Statute documentation identifier:

Type	<input type="text" value="Type2"/>
Value	<input type="text" value="Value2"/>
Role	<input type="text" value="Role2"/>

Statute note

Save

Next

Cancel

filename	dc.title	dcterms.issued	dc.subject	dc.subject	dcterms.isPartOf	dc.format
objects/2016010	MM01	01/01/2015	Register	PDF	Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q1	pdf/pdf
objects/Bradfor	MM02	02/01/2015	Register	EXCEL	Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q2	vnd.ms-excel/xls
objects/merton	MM03	03/01/2015	Register	WORD	Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q3	msword/doc

```

<?xml version="1.0" encoding="ASCII"?>
- <mets:mets xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.loc.gov/METS/
http://www.loc.gov/standards/mets/version18/mets.xsd" xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink"
xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xmlns:mets="http://www.loc.gov/METS/">
  <mets:metsHdr CREATEDATE="2016-07-01T14:18:41"/>
  - <mets:dmdSec ID="dmdSec_1">
    - <mets:mdWrap MDTYPE="DC">
      - <mets:xmlData>
        - <dcterms:dublincore xsi:schemaLocation="http://purl.org/dc/terms/
http://dublincore.org/schemas/xmls/qdc/2008/02/11/dcterms.xsd"
xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/" xmlns:dcterms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/">
          <dc:title>MM01</dc:title>
          <dcterms:issued>01/01/2015</dcterms:issued>
          <dc:subject>Register</dc:subject>
          <dc:subject>PDF</dc:subject>
          <dcterms:isPartOf>Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q1</dcterms:isPartOf>
          <dc:format>pdf/pdf</dc:format>
        </dcterms:dublincore>
      </mets:xmlData>
    </mets:mdWrap>
  </mets:dmdSec>
  - <mets:dmdSec ID="dmdSec_2">
    - <mets:mdWrap MDTYPE="DC">
      - <mets:xmlData>
        - <dcterms:dublincore xsi:schemaLocation="http://purl.org/dc/terms/
http://dublincore.org/schemas/xmls/qdc/2008/02/11/dcterms.xsd"
xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/" xmlns:dcterms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/">
          <dc:title>MM02</dc:title>
          <dcterms:issued>02/01/2015</dcterms:issued>
          <dc:subject>Register</dc:subject>
          <dc:subject>EXCEL</dc:subject>
          <dcterms:isPartOf>Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q2</dcterms:isPartOf>
          <dc:format>vnd.ms-excel/xls</dc:format>
        </dcterms:dublincore>
      </mets:xmlData>
    </mets:mdWrap>
  </mets:dmdSec>
  - <mets:dmdSec ID="dmdSec_3">
    - <mets:mdWrap MDTYPE="DC">
      - <mets:xmlData>
        - <dcterms:dublincore xsi:schemaLocation="http://purl.org/dc/terms/
http://dublincore.org/schemas/xmls/qdc/2008/02/11/dcterms.xsd"
xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/" xmlns:dcterms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/">
          <dc:title>MM03</dc:title>
          <dcterms:issued>03/01/2015</dcterms:issued>
          <dc:subject>Register</dc:subject>
          <dc:subject>WORD</dc:subject>
          <dcterms:isPartOf>Ministry of XYZ Report 4, 2016, Q3</dcterms:isPartOf>
          <dc:format>msword/doc</dc:format>
        </dcterms:dublincore>
      </mets:xmlData>
    </mets:mdWrap>
  </mets:dmdSec>

```

```

- <mets:rightsMD ID="rightsMD_2">
  - <mets:mdWrap MDTYPE="PREMIS:RIGHTS">
    - <mets:xmlData>
      - <premis:rightsStatement xsi:schemaLocation="info:lc/xmlns/premis-v2
        http://www.loc.gov/standards/premis/v2/premis-v2-2.xsd"
        xmlns:premis="info:lc/xmlns/premis-v2">
        - <premis:rightsStatementIdentifier>
          <premis:rightsStatementIdentifierType>UUID</premis:rightsStatementIdentifierType>
          <premis:rightsStatementIdentifierValue>cc189418-5aa8-4836-baab-
            34aa31a883f0</premis:rightsStatementIdentifierValue>
        </premis:rightsStatementIdentifier>
        <premis:rightsBasis>Copyright</premis:rightsBasis>
        - <premis:copyrightInformation>
          <premis:copyrightStatus>Copyright Status Test</premis:copyrightStatus>
          <premis:copyrightJurisdiction>Copyright jurisdiction Test</premis:copyrightJurisdiction>
          <premis:copyrightStatusDeterminationDate>2016-07-
            01</premis:copyrightStatusDeterminationDate>
          <premis:copyrightNote>Copyright note test</premis:copyrightNote>
          - <premis:copyrightDocumentationIdentifier>
            <premis:copyrightDocumentationIdentifierType>Type1</premis:copyrightDocumentationIdentifierType>
            <premis:copyrightDocumentationIdentifierValue>Value1</premis:copyrightDocumentationIdentifierValue>
            <premis:copyrightDocumentationRole>Role1</premis:copyrightDocumentationRole>
          </premis:copyrightDocumentationIdentifier>
          - <premis:copyrightApplicableDates>
            <premis:startDate>2016-07-01</premis:startDate>
            <premis:endDate>OPEN</premis:endDate>
          </premis:copyrightApplicableDates>
        </premis:copyrightInformation>
        - <premis:rightsGranted>
          <premis:act>Act1</premis:act>
          <premis:restriction>Allow</premis:restriction>
          - <premis:termOfGrant>
            <premis:startDate>2016-07-01</premis:startDate>
            <premis:endDate>OPEN</premis:endDate>
          </premis:termOfGrant>
          <premis:rightsGrantedNote>Restriction Note Test</premis:rightsGrantedNote>
        </premis:rightsGranted>
        - <premis:linkingObjectIdentifier>
          <premis:linkingObjectIdentifierType>UUID</premis:linkingObjectIdentifierType>
          <premis:linkingObjectIdentifierValue>81218b89-5ae3-4611-8ceb-
            0640024cb72a</premis:linkingObjectIdentifierValue>
        </premis:linkingObjectIdentifier>
      </premis:rightsStatement>
    </mets:xmlData>
  </mets:mdWrap>
</mets:rightsMD>

```

5) jkb-MD-Test2-yesCSV-yesRightsMD_160701

01.07.2018

Descriptive Metadata			
Descriptive Metadata Section	<dmdSec>	12x	
External Descriptive Metadata	<mdRef>	no	
Internal Descriptive Metadata	<mdWrap>	+100x	
Administrative Metadata			
Administrative Metadata Section	<amdSec>	66x	
Technical Metadata	<techMD>	18x	
IPR Metadata	<rightsMD>	27	
Source Metadata	<sourceMD>	no	
Digital Provenance Metadata	<digiprovMD>	+100x	
File Section			
File Section	<fileSec>	2x	
File Group	<fileGrp>	8x	
Structural Map			
Structural Map	<structMap>	24x	
METS pointer	<mptr>	no	
File pointer	<fptr>	6x	
Structural Links			
Structural Links	<smLink>	no	
Behaviour Section			
Behavior	<behavior>	no	

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Dear Participant,

thank you very much for contributing to my research.

This survey is part of my dissertation to earn the grade of Master of Science in Digital Information Services at Aberystwyth University 2016.

Based on the Archivematica set-up of the NLW and ARCW project my dissertation aims to determine how to prepare and create a "fit for purpose" SIP for digital objects of welsh local authorities.

I have tested the transfer and ingest function of Archivematica with data-sets that represent the most common file types in welsh local authorities [based on the Digital Preservation Survey 2016 by Jake Henry], and investigated the METS files that Archivematica produces during the transfer and ingest phases.

You have been contacted because of your experiences with Archivematica, data submission and ingest issues, and guiding data producer to provide coherent data sets for transfer to the archives.

Based on the Producer-Archive Interface Methodology Abstract Standard (PAIMAS) and the Archivematica rights and metadata management I set up this online questionnaire to to gain insight on practical experiences, statements and opinions on rights management, metadata management and submission negotiation for digital data from local authorities.

Each questionnaire page features a couple of questions to a specific topic and is accompanied by the specific PAIMAS recommendation. The linked paragraph provides further information and specifies the intended direction of my question.

The provided text box is restricted to a limit of 500 words.

On the next page you will find information based on the research ethics of Aberystwyth University, accompanied by the consent agreement.

Next

Pause the interview

Leave and delete my data

[Jasmin K. Böhmer](#), Aberystwyth University - Department of Information Studies. 2016.

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Before you complete the Questionnaire, please note the following procedures about this study:

1. *Duration*: Completing the Questionnaire (7 topics) should take about 30 minutes of your time.
2. *Confidentiality*: All the information you give me will be treated confidentially.
3. *Anonymity*: All questionnaires will be anonymous and personal data removed at the transcription stage. No individuals or individual institution will be identified in my results. Any direct quotes included in the report (that is, quotes of the things captured in the questionnaire), will be used selectively and anonymously (that is, no one will be able to attribute/link the words to you).
4. *Data security*: The information will be kept securely, and for only as long as necessary to:
 - a) analyse the research data and
 - b) report on the research and its findings.
5. *A full report and a summary* of the research findings will be available via Thomas Perry Library, Aberystwyth University end of 2016.
6. *Consent*: If you complete and return the Questionnaire, then I will assume that you have given your Consent to take part in this study. That is,
 - i. you have read and understood the information in this paragraph about the study.**
 - ii. you can contact me** (via my contact details listed below) **if you have any questions or concerns about the questionnaire or the study.**
 - iii. you understand that participation in this study is voluntary and that you are free to withdraw from the study at any time, without giving any reason and without any of your rights being affected.**
 - iv. you understand that your responses will be treated confidentially and in confidence by the researcher.**
 - v. you understand that your responses will be treated anonymously.**
 - vi. you allow me to use your direct quotes (that is, statements you might write in the questionnaire) in anonymised in the study's report/write-up.**

This questionnaire will be available 18th July 2016 till 1st August 2016.

I look forward to hearing from you.

Thank you,

Jasmin K. Boehmer

jab93@aber.ac.uk
Digital Information Services (MSc) 2015/2016
Department of Information Studies
Aberystwyth University

Back

Next

Pause the interview

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1. Please enter your Personal Data here.

This information will be replaced by a unique ID and will not be published.

Name

Work Sector

Profession

Back

Next

Pause the interview

Leave and delete my data

[Jasmin K. Böhmer](#), Aberystwyth University - Department of Information Studies. 2016.

2. How does your institution provide authentic and secure data transfer to the Archive without altering crucial information such as “created” or “last modified” in the data property information during the transfer process?

Please see [Link to PDF: Producer-Archive Interface Methodology Abstract Standard, PDF pages 32-33.](#)

P-23 Identify requirements for confidentiality and authentication between Producer and Archive.

Back

Next

Pause the interview

Leave and delete my data

[Jasmin K. Böhrer](#), Aberystwyth University - Department of Information Studies. 2016.

3. Which of the following permissions between Producer and Archive are featured in deposit license/ agreement of your institution?

This is a multiple choice answer.

- copyright permission
- migration permission (for the purpose of preservation)
- emulation permission (for the purpose of preservation)

If not, how does your institution handle these points?

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Pause the interview

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4. How does your institution capture descriptive metadata and especially preservation relevant information such as: provenance, version history, creator history for the following scenarios?

And how are links between digital object and metadata provided and documented (e.g. csv, excel, or xml files)?

Please see [Link to PDF: Producer-Archive Interface Methodology Abstract Standard, PDF page 67.](#)

Figure A-5: Archival Information Package. Preservation Description Information (PDI)

b) digital objects managed in local file structures without an EDRMS

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Next

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5. Archivemata provides a set of rights to manage in the user interface.

How does your institution capture and manage the rights for “Copyright/ Statute/ License/ Donor/ Policy/ Other” currently?

Perhaps in a standardized format and machine processable?

Please see [Link to Webpage: Add PREMIS Rights in Archivemata](#), section “Add PREMIS Rights”.

Back

Next

Pause the interview

Leave and delete my data

6. How does your institution distinguish between intellectual property rights (IPR) management for access and preservation?

If not applicable: What is your personal opinion on providing agreements for preservation IPR (for the Archive) and access IPR (for the User) separately?

Example: The Archive is allowed to edit metadata and edit the file name with standardized inscription. The User is not allowed to create a commercial product with the used content.

Please see [Link to PDF: Producer-Archive Interface Methodology Abstract Standard, PDF page 34.](#)

P-29 Assess the problem of intellectual property.

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Next

Pause the interview

Leave and delete my data

7. How does your institution determine “designated communities” for local authority digital data?

If that is not defined, what is your personal attempt of a definition?

Please see [Link to PDF: Producer-Archive Interface Methodology Abstract Standard, PDF page 28.](#)

P-5 Identify the Designated Community.

Back

Next

Pause the interview

Leave and delete my data

[Jasmin K. Böhmer](#), Aberystwyth University - Department of Information Studies. 2016.

8. In your personal opinion: What use options should be available for local authority data objects in use scenarios?

Up to date the regular access and authorization rules while handling data and metadata are read (view and print off), create (new objects and elements), edit (alter and edit), and delete (remove, preferably with audit trail).

Haynes, D. (2004). Metadata for information management and retrieval. London: Facet. P.164-165

This is a multiple choice answer.

- READ
- CREATE
- EDIT
- DELETE

NONE of the above, because

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Next

Pause the interview

Leave and delete my data

[Jasmin K. Böhrer](#), Aberystwyth University - Department of Information Studies. 2016.

9. In your personal opinion: What use options should be available for local authority metadata in use scenarios?

Up to date the regular access and authorization rules while handling data and metadata are read (view and print off), create (new objects and elements), edit (alter and edit), and delete (remove, preferably with audit trail).

Haynes, D. (2004). Metadata for information management and retrieval. London: Facet. P.164-165

This is a multiple choice answer.

- READ
- CREATE
- EDIT
- DELETE

NONE of the abobve, because

Back

Next

Pause the interview

Leave and delete my data

[Jasmin K. Böhmer](#), Aberystwyth University - Department of Information Studies. 2016.

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Thank you for completing this questionnaire!

I would like to thank you very much for helping me.

Your answers were transmitted, you may close the browser window or tab now.

[Jasmin K. Böhmer](#), Aberystwyth University - Department of Information Studies. 2016.

Appendix C: Examples Qualitative Data Analysis

No	Response	Code Response
1	Depositor assigns Copyright and related rights	DaR
	Depositor shall permit reproduction, distribution, transmission, display and use reproductions of material	
	Emulation, Migration etc. not specifically stated	Ensm
2	Covered by Accession Form	DaR
	Emulation not specified	Ensm
3	No Answer	NA
4	Not sure, born digital might require migration permission	MP
5	Usually Copyright is retained by the depositor	DrR

Themes	Codes	Statistics	Result
Depositor assigns Rights	DaR	Frequency	
Emulation not specifically mentioned	Ensm	Depositor assigns Rights	2
Depositor retains Rights	DrR	Emulation not specifically mentioned	2
Migration Permission	MP	Depositor retains Rights	1
No Answer	NA	Migration Permission	1
		No Answer	1
		TOTAL	7
		Proportion	
		Depositor assigns Rights	28.57%
		Emulation not specifically mentioned	28.57%
		Depositor retains Rights	14.29%
		Migration Permission	14.29%
		No Answer	14.29%
		TOTAL	100.00%

Appendix D: List of unanswered PAIMAS actions

Action No.	Action Title
P-1	Identify the contact persons and work organization
P-2	Exchange of general information
P-8	Assess the feasibility and co
P-15	Assess the efforts and associated costs
P-17	Define the Rules
P-18	Assess the associated costs
P-22	Assess the associated costs
P-27	Assess the associated costs
P-31	Address Archive Certification
P-32	Provide the standards and tools used
P-33	Assess the associated costs.
P-36	Assess associated costs
P-38	Study Validation Tool
P-39	Study quality methods
P-40	Assess associated costs
P-41	Define Preliminary Schedule
P-42	Assess permanent impact and associated costs
P-43	Carry out a cost summary, estimate risks
P-44	Assess the critical Points
P-45	Draw up a summary document
P-46	Make a preliminary agreement to proceed to the next phase